

CMR Working Papers

137/195

KAROLINA NIKIELSKA-SEKUŁA

CULTURAL HERITAGE PARTICIPATION PATTERNS OF UKRAINIANS IN POLAND AND POLES IN NORWAY

January 2025

www.migracje.uw.edu.pl

Abstract

This report presents findings from an MSCA-funded project *Cultural Heritage Participation Patterns among Immigrants and Their Influence on Integration. The Case of Ukrainians in Poland and Poles in Norway* (HerInt). First, it identifies and describes the patterns of participation in cultural heritage by migrants from Poland to Norway and from Ukraine to Poland – two European countries with different integration policy models, based on the data collected in qualitative photo-elicitation interviews. Secondly, it analyses the cultural policy of Norway and Poland from the perspective of the cultural inclusion of migrants, trying to understand how it could have influenced the cultural heritage participation patterns. Finally, it evaluates the relationship between cultural heritage participation patterns and migrants' emplacement in their respective new homelands, based on the correlation of cultural heritage participation patterns and the emplacement index of the participants to the study. Overall, the report aims to bridge the gap between migration and heritage studies by addressing the relevance of cultural heritage participation patterns to the issues of migrants' emplacement. Its goal is to deliver knowledge on the topic and initiate an interdisciplinary and cross-sectorial dialogue between migration and heritage scholars and cultural heritage stakeholders. The report ends with practical policy recommendations on including migrants through cultural heritage.

Keywords: Migration, Cultural heritage, Emplacement, Poles in Norway, Ukrainians in Poland.

Słowa kluczowe: Migracje, Dziedzictwo Kulturowe, Integracja, Polacy w Norwegii, Ukraińcy w Polsce.

Table of Contents

Introduction	4
Theoretical Framework and Research Objectives	4
Literature Review: Bridging the Gap between Migration and Heritage Studies	4
Research Objectives	6
Theoretical Framework: Cultural Heritage and Emplacement	7
Methodology and Context	8
Photo-elicitation Interviews and Ethnographic Observation	8
Descriptive Statistics	10
Document Analyses, Expert Interviews, Ethnographic Observation of the Cultural Field	11
Context and Sample	12
Positionality of the Researcher	15
Ethical Considerations	17
Findings	17
Migrant Minorities in Polish and Norwegian Cultural Policy	17
Introduction	17
Method	18
Polish Cultural Policy towards Migrating People	19
Norwegian Cultural Policy towards Migrating People	25
Polish and Norwegian Cultural Policy and Immigrant Minorities – Conclusions	30
Getting to Know Cultural Heritage Participation Patterns	32
Figure 1 Cultural Heritage Participation Patterns Model	34
Cultural Heritage Participation Patterns: Distribution in the Researched Population	34
Cultural Heritage Participation Patterns and Emplacement	47
Emplacement Index	47
Relationship Between the Emplacement Index and Cultural Heritage Participation Types	55
Discussion and Conclusions	58
Conclusions	59
Policy Recommendations	61
Appendices	68

Introduction

How do people engage with ancestral and new homeland heritage post-migration and what factors stand behind their heritage participation patterns? Can cultural heritage participation facilitate the emplacement process in the new country, and if so, how? These are the central research questions addressed in this paper. It aims to present the types of participation in cultural heritage by Poles in Norway and by Ukrainians in Poland, evaluating their influence on people's inclusion in their new homelands. By doing so, it attempts to bridge the gap between migration and heritage studies by addressing the relevance of cultural heritage participation patterns to the issues of emplacement of the migrants. Emplacement, after Çağlar and Glick Schiller (2018: 20–21), relates to the local place-making of people as they settle in new localities.

Theoretical Framework and Research Objectives

Literature Review: Bridging the Gap between Migration and Heritage Studies

Culture, and especially cultural heritage, as an indicator of autochthonous belonging (Geschiere 2009), has gained importance as a way of talking about a racialised idea of the nation (Balibar et al. 1991; Wikan 1999). The access to and recognition of cultural heritage within nation-states determines belonging on a socio-cultural level. In this light, cultural heritage gains meaning as a potential factor in the emplacement of migrants deserving scholarly attention.

While researchers on migration have tended to focus on the role of civic and socio-economic rights, e.g. access to citizenship, welfare services and the labour market in the post-migration emplacement of people, the scholarship on the relationship between emplacement and cultural heritage participation of migrating people is far less explored. The discussion of immigrants' heritage in an analytical rather than descriptive manner is deeply limited in migration studies. A large number of studies use the word "heritage" as an adjective standing for a background culture. These studies do not employ a theoretical framework of heritage studies to highlight the difference between cultural heritage and culture, treating them rather as synonymous. This means that they fail to problematise the link between heritage practices and actors' identity. However, as Macdonald (2013: 54) argues, cultural heritage is not equal to culture. Culture is something we can learn and be enculturated in. Its processual and dynamic character is recognised in public and scholarly debates (Gupta & Ferguson 2008). Heritage, on the other hand, focuses on "where you come from", referring to essentialised group identities. Heritage,

therefore, constitutes those elements of culture that are consciously marked by individuals and groups as inherited from ancestors and crucial for the preservation of a group identity for future generations. Culture, in turn, features practices, ideas and customs not all of which are important for identity. Traditionally understood, cultural heritage touches upon supposedly the most essentialist aspects of people's identities, "things that matter a lot to some people and that are bound up with their sense of who they are" (Macdonald 2013: 53), and may mediate the process of emplacement of those who migrate and settle in new countries. With the distinction between heritage and culture in mind, discussion on a broadly understood immigrant culture that has swept through the migration studies does not suffice in addressing the questions arising around heritage practices and their relationship with emplacement. Following this, migration studies have a significant knowledge gap relating to the identification of the way people who migrate engage with cultural heritage and heritage's relationship with the emplacement process. This working paper wishes to contribute to this knowledge gap by discussing the relationship between heritage participation patterns by people with a migration background and their emplacement process to the new homeland, based on empirical research conducted.

The heritage field of study has been interested in investigating issues around cultural heritage and migration for a long time. A large and developed body of literature has focused on the representation and protection of minority heritage within institutionalised "heritage spaces" (Arokiasamy 2012; Prescott 2018; Innocenti 2014; Neyrinck 2017; Nettleford 2004; van der Zeijden et al. 2017). This discussion was oriented on institutional heritage, often linking it to supranational debates at a European level. A joint account of archaeology and heritage studies has focused on the heritage management of minorities with regard to the institutional, theoretical and ethical approaches to heritage in a changing world (Holtorf et. al. 2018). Additionally, analyses of heritage in the context of multiculturalism have gained attention in relation to the issues of ethnicity, race and nationalism (Leung 2006; Gnecco 2015). These studies critically discussed the incorporation of minority heritage into the mainstream on an institutional level, developing new theoretical approaches to heritage such as "cross-cultural heritage" (Colomer et al. 2018), and multicultural heritage as representing humanity at large (Gnecco 2015). These works, while giving an insight into institutional approaches to the heritages of immigrants, provide limited insight into patterns of cultural heritage participation by those who migrate and settle in new countries, namely their micro practices relating to heritage expression. While attempts to move the discussion on the heritage of migrants beyond the institutional context by analysing actors' actual heritage practices have been made by some

scholars (Colomer 2017; Mohamed et al. n.d.; Nikielska-Sekula 2019; Banaszekiewicz & Nikielska-Sekula 2024), little is known about the socio-demographic factors shaping particular patterns of cultural heritage participation by migrating people, including the relationship between heritage participation and emplacement outcomes. Additionally, to the best of my knowledge, a theoretical model describing the engagement of migrating people in heritage post-migration does not exist. What is more, according to the criticism voiced by Byrne (2016) heritage scholars often fail to employ migration theories in their analyses of migrating people's heritage, resulting in keeping the discussion within the constraints of methodological nationalism (Wimmer & Glick Schiller 2002). This working paper aims to address these issues through presenting the research findings with the acknowledgement of developments in both, the heritage and migration studies.

Research Objectives

Recognising the presented research gaps, this research project aimed to bridge the gap between migration and heritage studies through the inclusion of cultural heritage participation patterns in scholarly debates on the emplacement of migrants. The specific objectives of the discussed research are:

- 1) To identify the types of cultural heritage participation by migrating people with reference to their demographic, cultural, and economic background;
- 2) To evaluate the influence of a country-specific cultural policy regarding the culture of its immigrant minorities on the migrating people's cultural heritage participation patterns. More specifically, the interest here is put on the policy regarding cultural expression by immigrant minorities, protection of their culture, and the incorporation of immigrant minorities into mainstream cultural production.
- 3) To identify whether there is a relation between the patterns of cultural heritage participation and migrating people's emplacement outcomes.

While the individual outcomes of emplacement are influenced by the overall policies of the new homeland and the individual background of the actors, this working paper investigates the relationship between the cultural heritage participation patterns and emplacement. What is more, based on the collected data, it produces a model of cultural heritage participation of migrating people, indicating the influences of country-specific cultural policies and individual background characteristics on this model. The model of cultural heritage participation patterns

was created inductively based on respondents' practices focused on the engagement with the heritage of their new and ancestral homelands. To the best of my knowledge, no similar model describing how exactly migrating people participate in cultural heritage exists.

Theoretical Framework: Cultural Heritage and Emplacement

Conceptual analyses regarding cultural heritage participation patterns in this working paper are based on processual approaches to cultural heritage, according to which heritage is seen as a process and performance (Harvey 2001; Smith 2016; Harrison et al. 2020). The core argument here reflects the view that practices of people engaging with material heritage objects are the core of cultural heritage, as without them the tangible and intangible objects of heritage lose their meaning and importance (Smith 2016). Heritage, therefore, always represents a performative practice (Smith 2021: 40). The concept of '*heritage in becoming*' (Nikielska-Sekula 2019) was employed in this study to approach the heritage performance of the respondents participating in the interviews conducted as part of the discussed research. Heritage in becoming refers to engaging with the environment by improvising and imitating ancestors' practices, thereby representing a practical implementation of inherited practices in adjustment to the local circumstances the individuals and groups find themselves within. These heritage practices undergo a constant process of change, rather than representing a stable pattern of traditions passed down from generation to generation, which makes the concept suitable for analyses of migrant people's everyday heritage practices beyond the institutional framework and as responding to the day-to-day circumstances.

In addition, the lenses of a transnational social field perspective (Levitt et al. 2004) are utilised to approach the heritage practices of the respondents beyond the constraints of methodological nationalism (Wimmer and Glick Schiller 2002). Following the view on the practices and heritage performances of people who migrate as not limited by the national borders, the transnational links and practices of the respondents are acknowledged in the conceptualisation of their cultural heritage participation patterns. Additionally, a concept of emplacement is employed and understood as "a person's efforts, within the barriers and opportunities that contingencies of local place-making offer, to build a life within networks of local, national, supranational, and global interconnections" (Çağlar and Glick Schiller 2018: 20–21). Emplacement is employed to describe the process of the respondents' settlement in the new country.

Finally, the concepts from heritage and migration studies are supported by a translocational positionality perspective (Anthias 2008) going beyond a reductionist view of the identities of migrants, acknowledging various roles and positions the individuals negotiate between. Translocational positionality was employed to assess the respondents' backgrounds and it describes the way individual positionalities could have influenced cultural heritage participation patterns.

Overall, the theoretical framework supports processual approaches to heritage derived from Critical Heritage Studies, utilises the transnational view on the migration process and recognises the varying positionalities of the respondents.

Methodology and Context

The overall methodology of the HerInt research employed a mixed-method approach. Methodology is presented for clarity in full below, offering an overview of how and why qualitative data were turned into quantitative ones, while this report **specifically presents the findings from statistical analyses conducted on the data collected qualitatively**. Qualitative analyses of the data, in turn, are presented in other publications.

Primary empirical data were collected through qualitative interviews employing visual and sensory methods including photo-elicitation, photo survey and mapping, supported by an ethnographic observation of cultural heritage events to which the researcher was invited by the participants, or participated through open access channels. The methodology employed was tailored to research minority culture beyond essentialism (Çağlar 1997) and to sustain the balance between recognition and essentialism (Appiah 1994), adding to the emerging discussion on the potential of multisensory methods in the migration field (Nikielska-Sekula & Desille 2021). The interviews sourced the data for descriptive statistical analyses. Additionally, a thematic analysis was conducted on the policy documents, along with expert interviews and ethnographic observations in the cultural institutions in Poland and Norway. Below, I describe each component of the methodology in detail.

Photo-elicitation Interviews and Ethnographic Observation

The interviews were based on and guided by photographs depicting elements of cultural heritage prepared by the respondents before the interview and brought to the interview meeting.

The information given to participants before the interview requested them to prepare images for discussion (pictures and videos that represented elements of their cultural heritage).

To support photo-elicitation and ensure information of interest was obtained about issues not covered by the pictures brought by the respondents, the interview guide was designed to deliver data on people's practices around cultural heritage engagement (in relation to both the ancestral and new homelands, as well as globalised heritage). The questions asked focused on the respondents' engagement in traditions, national day celebrations, cultural events participation, language maintenance, food, music, sensory heritage (smells, tastes) and material heritage. Additionally, their background characteristics (gender, age, occupation, etc.) and specific emplacement outcomes (new homeland's language proficiency, mapping of social networks, feeling of belonging in the new homeland, labour market integration, etc.) were collected. What is more, the research was interested in establishing transnational and local social connections of the respondents. In this regard, a mental map method was introduced. The respondents were asked to draw a map of their social relations, marking people they maintained contact with and their geographical location. The interview guide is presented in Appendices 3 and 4.

Data collected from the interviews were supported by multisensory ethnographic observation during the events and social situations I was invited to by the respondents. These included visits to closed ethnic festivals organised by them, private social meetings and visits to open public gatherings of the members of the diaspora. This information served as a useful context and deepened the understanding of the researched situation, yet it was not directly involved in the conceptualisation of the cultural heritage participation types.

Qualitative interviews and collected visual data were interpreted and analysed using MAX QDA software and taking a thematic coding approach. The analyses allowed the inductive creation of cultural heritage participation patterns based on the declared practices of the respondents.

Based on interview data, each respondent was classified into a category in each of three dimensional cultural heritage participation patterns. Background information for the purposes of the emplacement index, as well as demographic background, were also retrieved from the interviews and used in correlations.

While qualitative analyses leading to the creation of cultural heritage participation patterns are beyond the scope of this paper and are presented in other publications, a substantial overview

of all the dimensions of qualitatively created categorisation is described further to facilitate an understanding of the qualitative context of the research. The decision to quantify the qualitative data was driven by the desire to indicate the relationship between demographic background and emplacement outcomes and cultural heritage participation categories, in order to assess whether emplacement can be supported by cultural heritage engagement. Statistical correlations addressed this goal adequately in terms of systemic analyses. Their findings are described further and, when relevant, are substantiated with findings from the qualitative analysis, though this is not presented in this report.

In total, 106 interviews were collected, 50 with Ukrainians in Poland and 56 with Poles in Norway. Of these, 103 were selected for further analyses. Respondents were recruited through snowball sampling, starting with cultural associations of minorities, and through the personal contacts of the researcher and research assistants, as well as through online channels.

Descriptive Statistics

The evaluation of the relationship between cultural heritage participation patterns and (1) emplacement index on the one hand, and (2) demographic data, including the positionality of the respondents on the other, was based on quantitative methods such as descriptive statistics, analyses of correlation and logistical regression. Qualitative data were transformed into quantitative indicators in the following way:

1) cultural heritage participation patterns were treated as a categorical variable covering patterns-categories identified in the qualitative analysis based on declared engagement or a lack thereof in the tangible and intangible heritage of new and ancestral homelands and beyond.

2) Other variables were derived from the declared background and demographic information, classified into categories with subcategories declared by the respondents specifying, where relevant: gender, age, labour market status, compliance of education with occupation, education level, family status, length of stay in the new homeland, declared belonging and self and group identification.

3) The emplacement index was based on data obtained in qualitative analyses regarding fluency in the language and participation in cultural events in the new homeland, labour market

participation, approaches to obtaining citizenship in the new homeland, feeling of belonging, local and transnational social networks, self and group identification, and participation in cultural events. The emplacement index is described in detail in the analytical part of this working paper.

Background and demographic variables and index outcomes were correlated with cultural heritage participation patterns with the help of descriptive statistics and correlation measures.

[Document Analyses, Expert Interviews, Ethnographic Observation of the Cultural Field](#)

Expert interviews with heritage stakeholders were conducted, regarding events and activities addressing and oriented towards migrants, along with document analyses with a focus on comparing cultural policies in Poland and Norway with regard to migrant minorities' right to cultural expression and their inclusion into the mainstream cultural discourse. Additionally, ethnographic observations in cultural institutions offering activities to migrant people were also conducted in Poland and Norway. In total, five expert interviews were conducted in Poland – three as written/corresponding interviews, one online and one in person. In Norway, expert interviews were replaced by ethnographic observation on the difficulties in establishing contacts for online interviews with the relevant stakeholders and NGOs. This also led to the decision to conduct parallel field observations in Poland. Field observations were treated as a way to assess the implementation of the policy in the field.

Expert interviews targeted NGOs and stakeholders working with migrant populations in Poland and Norway and were oriented on the type of activities offered, funding schemes and reasoning behind targeting the migrant population in cultural activities. As mentioned, this was supported by the field observation in cultural institutions mapped as crucial from the point of view of migrating people's cultural involvement. The observation included collecting memos from the field, along with visual documentation of the facilities and the offer on display. The details of this observation are presented in the analytical part of the paper. Collected data was used to assess the way policy was implemented in the field.

Document analyses targeted governmental documents regarding cultural policy, or including fragments describing/formulating cultural policy. Documents were sourced from the official governmental webpages in Norway and Poland (gov.pl, isap.sejm.gov.pl, and regjeringen.no). The detailed sampling method regarding the documents in the respective countries is explained

in the analytical part of the working paper. Automated lexical analyses were conducted on the selected documents, targeting issues of interest with the help of the MaxDictio tool in MaxQda software. The sections of interest were then analysed with substantial thematic coding and the findings are presented further.

Context and Sample

Poles in Norway and Ukrainians in Poland were respectively the largest groups of foreign residents in their new homelands at the time of conducting the research (Brunarska et.al 2016; SSB 2024). In both countries, their migration had been mostly labour-driven, but for Ukrainians in Poland there was a sharp shift from labour migrants to temporary protection beneficiaries after the start of Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022. Norway represents de-facto multiculturalism, generally replicating the European multicultural model based on ethnonational states. It has a long tradition of being a receiving country and immigration policies have been developed there since 1974 (Brochmann & Hagelund 2012). Poland, traditionally an emigration country, has only recently become a receiving country on a big scale (Górny, et al. 2019). At the time when the research was conducted, its integration policy was still taking shape, being first formulated in 2012 (Brunarska et. al. 2016: 116).

The interviews with Poles in Norway were conducted between March and October 2020 and October 2021 and March 2022 in Polish – the language that the researcher, research assistants and respondents were fluent in. Three interviews were conducted offline, in my house in Norway – at the request of the respondents. The other interviews were conducted online – this was induced by the sanitary regimes due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and later continued as the preferred form of communication by the respondents. Interviews with Poles in Norway were conducted by me and three research assistants – all Polish. In total, we collected 56 interviews, 53 of which were included in the analyses.

Interviews with Ukrainians in Poland were conducted between May and November 2023 by me and two research assistants – one Polish, and one Ukrainian. They were conducted in Polish with those who were comfortable speaking Polish, and in Ukrainian with those who preferred. The interviews were conducted in the respondents' houses, online or in public places such as cafeterias etc. Initially, interviews with Ukrainians in Poland were oriented solely on labour migrants. Right before the project started, however, the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine occurred and the project team decided not to exclude those arriving as refugees from

participation in the study. The reasons behind it included evidence in existing research that the motives for migration are often mixed, with the line between mixing migration motivations being difficult to draw (Van Hear, Brubaker & Bessa 2009). This mixed nature of Ukrainians' migration to Poland was confirmed in the field. While many came for the first time due to the full-scale war, they quickly found jobs and integrated into the Polish labour market. Additionally, educational migrants from Ukraine to Poland, who left Poland to visit families in Ukraine for their winter break, arrived back after 22 February 2022, receiving temporary protection status. In total, we collected 50 interviews with Ukrainians.

Overall, 103 interviews were selected for further analyses, 53 with Poles in Norway and 50 with Ukrainians in Poland. The similarities in the sample – a mostly labour-driven nature of migration, a European background of the migrants and mainstream society, relative cultural proximity and insignificance of racialised embodied characteristics – allowed for joint analyses of the two subsamples. Still, the sample was analysed both jointly and with a division into the countries of settlement, in order to grasp any potential discrepancies. If any discrepancies were identified, it was explained with the help of the qualitative analyses of cultural policy towards migrants in the respective destination countries and the background characteristics of the subsamples. This allowed me to show trends in participating in cultural heritage in the sample, with an indication of what mediates them in terms of demography, migration profile, as well as the country of destination's policy. Regarding the sample, women outnumbered men, with 78 women and 25 men; 53.4% of the respondents had no children, 20.4% had one child, 22.3% had two children and 1.9% had respectively three or four children. The average age was 33 years old (with 34 as the median age). The overwhelming majority of the respondents had a good command of the mainstream language of the new country of settlement, with only 4% declaring their language skills as weak, and 1.9 % (two people) who said they are non-speakers of the mainstream language. There were 12 respondents who had citizenship of the country of settlement, the rest did not (88%). Almost 75% of the respondents declared that they had academic degrees, with 23% having secondary and vocational education. Over 90% were in work at the time of the interview.

Overview of sample's socio-demographic characteristics		
Gender	Woman	75.7 % (78 people)
	Man	24.3 % (25 people)
Parental status	No children	53.4% (55 people)
	Parent to one child	20.4% (21 people)
	Parent to two children	22.3% (23 people)
	Parent to three children	1.9% (2 people)
	Parent to four children	1.9 % (2 people)
Age	Average in the sample	33 years old
	Median in the sample	34 years old
Mainstream language skills	Fluent	64.1 % (66 people)
	Very good	14.6 % (15 people)
	Communicative	14.6 (15 people)
	Weak	4.9% (5 people)
	Non speakers	1.9 % (2 people)
Citizenship	Citizens	11.7% (12 people)
	Non-citizens	88.3 % (91 people)
Education	Higher (academic degree)	74.8 % (77 people)
	Secondary and vocational	23.3 % (24 people)
	Primary	1.9 % (2 people)
Employment status	Employed	90.3 % (93 people)
	Unemployed	9.7 % (10 people)

When it comes to differences between the countries of settlement, the populations had overall similar characteristics: in both countries, women outnumbered men, the majority worked, citizenship rates were low, while command of the mainstream language of the country of settlement was high. However, there are some nuances worth mentioning. For instance, while the majority of respondents did not have citizenship of the new country of settlement, there were more Ukrainians (11) who had Polish citizenship than Poles who had Norwegian citizenship (3). In addition, more Ukrainians (7) than Poles (3) did not work at all. Ukrainians in Poland also more often worked outside of their occupation than Poles in Norway did. Additionally, the median length of stay by Ukrainians in the new country was shorter by approx. three years than that of Poles in Norway. However, when divided into gender, Ukrainian men and Polish men had similar lengths of stay, while Ukrainian women had a four-year shorter settlement period on average in Poland, compared to Polish women in Norway. This was clearly

caused by the fact that there were eight newly arrived refugees in the subsample of Ukrainians in Poland and all of them were female. What is more, the Ukrainian-Polish sample had, on average, fewer children (0.5 for Ukrainians and 1.1 for Poles on average).

Overall, the sample description tells us that recruited people were active in the labour market, had higher or secondary education and spoke the language of the country of settlement. The sample, as a whole, is analysed jointly as similarities between the profiles of populations in Poland and Norway make comparisons possible, though some comparisons between the subsamples in the two countries of the settlement are made too when relevant differences occur.

In Poland, interviews with experts were conducted in the area of Krakow, due to its proximity to the Ukrainian border and a wide cultural offer oriented on Ukrainians. The same regarded the ethnographic observation in cultural institutions. In Norway, the initial plan was to use expert interviews from previous research, these data, however, were permanently lost due to a technical issue. After failing to establish contacts with Norwegian stakeholders online, an ethnographic observation in cultural institutions in the area of Oslo, where the highest population of immigrants was registered (Gulbrandsen et al. 2021), was conducted.

Positionality of the Researcher

The presented research was conducted in two destinations – Poland and Norway. In both, I presented different positionality. In Norway, I was an immigrant from Poland, working as a highly skilled professional, with proficiency in Norwegian and an advanced knowledge of Norwegian society and culture – which I studied and taught at the local university. I migrated to Norway after concluding my MA studies in Poland and had lived there for nine years at the time of data collection, with some study visits in third countries during this period. I had no or limited experience of working in Poland and having a post-graduated family life there. I therefore assimilated to the modes of doing these everyday activities in Norway. While researching Poles in Norway, I was seen as a community member and the first respondents originated from similar socio-cultural and economic backgrounds to mine. To diversify the sample, I hired assistants – students from Poland, who shared Polish identity and language with the respondents, yet were not familiar with Norway. It helped diversify the sample, but it also resulted in extended explanations of Norwegian culture and values by the respondents to the assistants in the interviews – something I did not experience in my interviews. The data collected in Norway was mostly collected during my employment at the University of South-

Eastern Norway and the respondents knew that the research was legitimised by a Norwegian academic institution. I believe that this facilitated the recruitment of respondents, who were concerned about ethical issues and anonymity. Many of the respondents saw me as an expert in migration and citizenship issues; often, during and after the interview, they asked me questions regarding obtaining citizenship in Norway and other similar practical issues. Being non-Norwegian, I induced quite open and sometimes critical stances about Norwegian society and there were a lot of references to the shared experience of being a Pole in Norway between myself and the respondents. Some invited me to their private gatherings, as part of ethnographic observation, but most retained the social distance common in Norway, meeting me only for the interview and primarily online. Upon receiving funding to continue this research, I relocated to Poland and my positionality shifted from being a minority member to a majority member. I represented the mainstream Polish society for many of the Ukrainian respondents, though some tried to connect with me through our shared migration experience, pointing out the hardship of migration. Being an outsider to the community shaped the responses in the interview – explanations of Ukrainian culture were common during the interview, to make me understand what the respondents were telling me about. In addition, across the interviewees I observed a very positive attitude towards Poland – which might have been exaggerated in light of my assumed ethnic background. Interestingly, while in Norway, I was never invited to the houses, apart from some private gatherings I was granted access to, in Poland I was invited to the houses of the respondents for the interviews. During the interviews in Poland, I also hired assistants, one Polish-speaking and one Ukrainian-speaking.

In both phases of the research – Norwegian and Polish – my positionality influenced my interpretation of the field. I used a multisensory positionality to assess the cultural practices of the respondents. While being invited to their homes and gatherings I was offered food, I was able to smell the scents and assess the visual aesthetics of their homes. The familiarity and unfamiliarity of these experiences perceived by my sensory receptors positioned me as close or distant to their practices. Based on this, I made assumptions about how well the respondents merged into mainstream society. My positionality and migration and emplacement experience also influenced the design of the research. I was conscious that my methodological choices may come from my personal experience of migration and therefore I confronted the methodology and emplacement indicators with the literature on the topic and consulted it with other migration scholars. I therefore adjusted my methodological choices to the current state of the art, making sure they were research-based.

Regarding the document analysis method, I am fluent in Polish and Norwegian and therefore I was able to conduct the analyses in the native language of the documents selected for the sample.

Ethical Considerations

Participants to the interviews gave informed consent to participate in the research. The consent was supported by written information about the project (in Ukrainian and Polish – depending on the sample), data protection measures and GDPR. All personal data were processed in accordance with The Personal Data Protection Act enforced on 10 May 2018. The consent was recorded to avoid collecting unnecessary information such as surnames. The collection of interviews in Norway was approved by the NSD (Norwegian Centre for Research Data) and followed the ethical guidelines for social research issued by the Norwegian Ethics Committees. Further data collection in Poland, as well as the entire project, received a positive recommendation from the CMR-UW¹ Ethics Committee and followed principles of ethical research in the context of migration.

Findings

Migrant Minorities in Polish and Norwegian Cultural Policy

Introduction

This section presents the findings from document analyses regarding the approach of Polish and Norwegian Cultural Policy towards migrant minorities and their culture. In what follows, I present the detailed methodology of analyses, then I describe the threads recurring in the analyses and present a summary of core strategies of Polish and Norwegian Cultural Policy towards migrants. Then, I compare these results with the outcomes of the observation in Polish and Norwegian public institutions of culture regarding the implementation of cultural policy strategies.

¹ Centre of Migration Research at the University of Warsaw, where the research was conducted.

Method

The analyses were conducted in Norwegian and Polish – aligned to the language of the documents sourced in each country. For Norwegian cultural policy, with the help of search engines, I collected documents that included the word “*kulturpolitikk*” (cultural policy) at www.regjeringen.no. Out of the results, I chose the documents produced by the government – White Papers, Strategies, Proposals, and NOU reports (Norwegian Official Reports). I collected 66 documents issued regarding the period after 2010. For Polish cultural policy, I searched two governmental portals with policy documents – gov.pl and isap.sej.gov.pl focusing on those regarding cultural policy. Since the search engine at these websites did not allow me to identify documents that contained the word “*polityka kulturalna*” (cultural policy), I used the thematic keywords assigned to each document – “*kultura i sztuka*” (culture and arts) at isap.sej.gov.pl and “*polityka kulturalna*” (cultural policy) at gov.pl. This way, I gained access to documents classified as regarding cultural policy and culture and art that were governmental legal acts and/or strategies. In total, I collected 47 documents regarding the period after 2010. To these documents, I added documents classified as cultural policy strategy from before 2010 (7 additional documents) to see the continuity of cultural policy development after the transition (1989), and from a few references to the cultural inclusion of migrants settled in Poland in other documents. The year 2010 was chosen as the cut-off, because the period between 2010-2023 overlaps with the time of arrival of the majority of the respondents participating in qualitative interviews.

Selected documents (54 for Poland, 66 for Norway) were further analysed with the help of the MaxDictio tool in MaxQda software – the fragments of text containing sensitising words² were coded in the first stage. In the second stage, specific combinations of sensitising words that overlapped in the previously coded sections of the text³ were retrieved and coded. In the third phase, the fragments coded with MaxDictio were substantially analysed and coded according to the emerging themes.

² The following words and their expansions were used: For the search in Polish: *kultura, polityka, migrant, integracja, wielokulturowość, obcokrajowiec, uchodźca*. For the search in Norwegian: *kulturpolitikk, innvandring, migrant, integrering, mangfold*.

³ For Polish language: *kultura and polityka* as a phrase, as well as *kultura and polityka* separately combined with *migrant, integracja, wielokulturowość, obcokrajowiec, uchodźca*. For Norwegian language: *kulturpolitikk and innvandring, kulturpolitikk and migrant, kulturpolitikk and integrering, kulturpolitikk and mangfold*.

What is more, for each country, crucial cultural policy documents were identified and analysed with thematic coding. The list of these documents is presented in Appendix 1. The focus of this analysis was to define the core approaches of cultural policy towards migrants and their cultural participation in the mainstream cultural sector. The main threads regarding the cultural policy towards migrating people in Poland and Norway were retrieved. As expected, they overlapped with the threads identified in automated and substantial analyses of the set of selected documents and helped better understand and contextualise them. In what follows, I describe the findings from this analysis.

Polish Cultural Policy towards Migrating People

Polish cultural policy in the first years after the post-communist transformation (after 1989) had important challenges to overcome, including monument reprivatisation processes and combating prejudices towards the state's role in managing the cultural life of the country – which in the communist times was focused on censoring and propaganda purposes. The documents issued in the first years after the transformation did not address migrants settled in Poland and their inclusion in the Polish cultural scene, but rather focused on refining the understanding of cultural policy in post-communist Poland. The fact that Poland was not an immigration country back then, even if foreign-born inhabitants lived in Poland, is also explanatory of this. These early documents formulated strategies to participate in international cultural exchange within the frameworks of UNESCO and European and regional initiatives. There was also a focus on cultural exchange with the Polish diaspora abroad.⁴ Overall, the need to support the development of Polish culture and to refine the state's role in monitoring and supporting these initiatives, also financially, was recognised. Culture was seen as an important element of creating a national identity and this view has continued until today. Cultural exchange was limited to international cooperation, with the omission of foreign nationals inhabiting Poland, and was seen as a way to boost the cultural production of Poland – the quality and range of which was seen as unsatisfactory.

Later in the policy documents,⁵ culture started to be seen as a means of social integration: its potential was underlined in relation to the inclusion of vulnerable and marginalised populations, including people with disabilities and with economic difficulties. Culture was also seen as

⁴ *Polityka Kulturalna 1993; Zadania MKiS 1995-1999; Prezydencka karta kultury polskiej 1997*

⁵ *Narodowa Strategia Rozwoju Kultury na lata 2004-2013*

helpful in overcoming challenges connected to globalisation. Nevertheless, foreign-born inhabitants of Poland were not mentioned as targeted by these integrative potential of culture. An important aspect of cultural policy formulated around 2004 (the year of Poland's accession to the EU) was oriented on facilitating integration within the EU through culture. In these early documents, the instances where culture was seen as helpful in managing migration were limited to its role in preventing the emigration of Polish citizens from Poland and following the loss of cultural capital resulting from it.⁴

The first decade of the 2000s saw a focus on national minorities in Polish cultural policy and efforts to grant them equal access to culture, including access to funding offered to mainstream cultural institutions. Cultural diversity coming from the input of national minorities was seen as part of Polish cultural heritage.⁶

The document that first approached immigrants explicitly as part of the official cultural policy of the country was *Strategy of Social Capital Development 2020*⁷ issued in 2013. It acknowledged a growing influx of migrants to Poland, predicting that this tendency will continue to grow, and indicating the need for creating a policy that will support, among other things, the inclusion of migrating people in the cultural life of Poland.⁸ This document, however, failed to name specific implementation strategies to reach this goal. The tendency to focus on the Polish diaspora as a means to promote Polish culture abroad continued. What is more, volunteering and participation in sports activities were seen as an important tool to overcome discrimination and other challenges of contemporary Poland and enhance social integration. This recommendation had the potential to improve the situation of foreign-born inhabitants of Poland, though they were not mentioned explicitly as possible beneficiaries of this strategy.

Polish cultural policy in the 2010s continued orientation on national identity reproduction and did not open up to include migrant minorities as co-producers of the national culture. Migrating people's culture was not targeted by cultural policy documents, even if the presence of migrants was acknowledged there.⁹ The document from 2017¹⁰ contained more specific strategies regarding the cultural participation of migrating people, yet they were limited to their

⁶ *Uzupełnienie narodowej strategii rozwoju kultury na lata 2004-2020*: 72

⁷ *Strategia Rozwoju Kapitału Społecznego 2020*

⁸ *Ibid*: 31

⁹ *Strategia Rozwoju Kapitału Społecznego 2020*; *Uchwała Nr 8 Rady Ministrów z dnia 14 lutego 2017 r. w sprawie przyjęcia Strategii na rzecz Odpowiedzialnego Rozwoju do roku 2020*

¹⁰ *Uchwała Nr 8 Rady Ministrów z dnia 14 lutego 2017 r. w sprawie przyjęcia Strategii na rzecz Odpowiedzialnego Rozwoju do roku 2020*

incorporation into Polish culture. It suggested creating support for certain groups of migrants (prioritised in migration policies) in acquiring knowledge of the Polish language and culture.¹¹ A specific strategy to offer this support was proposed in relation to children coming from “migrant families” through organising preparatory departments at schools oriented on language acquisition and overcoming “problems in adaptation.” They aimed to facilitate a smooth transition into participation in regular school classes in Polish.¹² However, given the background culture of the migrating people, there was a lack of focus on their right to alternative cultural production inspired by their culture of origin. Neither were migrant people recognised as possible co-producers of Polish culture.

Overall, Polish cultural policy has not been particularly oriented toward migrants settled in Poland, even though their permanent presence in the country was recognised in the second half of the 2010s. While national minorities were recognised in the policy as entitled to the right of cultural expression and their culture was acknowledged as part of Polish culture, immigrant minorities were not granted such rights. The concern of cultural policy regarding migrants was rather oriented on educating them about Polish culture and customs. There were certain strategies named regarding the inclusion of non-Polish speaking children in the Polish education system through the creation of preparatory units organised at local schools, as well as recommendations to educate migrants settling in Poland about the Polish language and culture and through such education provide them with access to mainstream cultural life in Poland. The idea of making space for and supporting alternative cultural expressions of immigrant minorities has not been voiced in the policy, nor has the idea of recognising migrants’ background culture as an important source of inspiration for the mainstream Polish culture.

Immigrant Minorities’ Culture in Polish Cultural Policy – Summary of Focus Areas

Among the threads identified through the document analyses the following issues regarding the direct or indirect targeting of migrants through cultural policy were identified:

- Culture was recognised as a means to educate about tolerance and combat discrimination and racism.

¹¹ *Ibid*: 129

¹² *Ibid*: 208

Migrant people were not directly named as possible beneficiaries of this capacity of culture, though the strategies to enhance tolerance and combat racism and discrimination through cultural activities might work towards migrant minorities' inclusion through culture.

- Culture was recognised as a tool of social integration.

Cultural activities were seen as useful in creating social cohesion, which could have indirectly influenced migrant minorities, provided that they participated in culture. Migrants, however, were not named explicitly in this regard. Yet they were mentioned in the context of their integration through education about the Polish language and culture. Language acquisition and adjustment to Polish customs was seen as a desirable path for the cultural integration of migrants.

- The culture of national minorities was granted recognition and protection.

This is in contrast to the culture of migrant minorities, which has not received any attention in regard to protection guarantees, but it creates an important precedence and set of good practices that may in the future be transferred also to migrant minorities.

Implementation of Polish Cultural Policy Towards Immigrant Minorities – Remarks from Ethnographic Observation in Public Cultural Institutions and Interviews with Stakeholders

The way the cultural policy of Poland has been formulated throughout the three decades after 1989 did not give much hope for the inclusion of migrant people and their culture by mainstream cultural institutions. The observation in the field, however, brought quite surprising findings, uncovering a rich scene of cultural institutions and activities targeting migrants settled in Poland. Among them were initiatives oriented on providing space to celebrate minority culture, display the products of this culture, as well as create a meeting point for the local inhabitants, including those foreign-born, and stimulate intercultural dialogue between them.

As part of the field analyses, I conducted five expert interviews along with an ethnography of public cultural institutions in southern Poland. I also searched the internet and got acquainted with the activities of several bodies – public institutions and NGOs oriented on the culture of migrant people. As a unit of analysis, I chose Krakow and its neighbouring area, as this is where the majority of the respondents were recruited for the study in Poland. In the overwhelming majority of the cases, the cultural activities offered to immigrant minorities were financed with

public money – often through competitive grant funding schemes. These were international grants (from the European Union, Norway Grants, etc), but also money from local governing institutions, especially the Małopolska Voivodship. The share of money coming from the central government was scarce. Interestingly, some activities were also funded from private donations. I present some examples of activities below and draw some conclusions regarding the de facto cultural policy towards migrant minorities in Poland.

For instance, the public Voivodship Library in Kraków organised several activities targeted at refugees and/or Ukrainian nationals. It featured books in Ukrainian, organised literary meetings and reading clubs in Ukrainian, artistic workshops, Polish classes for Ukrainian seniors, therapy through art sessions, exhibitions of Ukrainian artists, and meetings for children-oriented on playful activities in Polish and around Polish culture. Similar activities and opportunities were organised by other local libraries in the neighbouring cities. It, therefore, seems that not only the strategy of Polish cultural policy to integrate through educating about the Polish language and culture is supported by local institutions, but also activities oriented on background culture maintenance and development of the migrants inhabiting Poland are widely organised. Public libraries in Krakow and the area served as a venue to maintain the ethnic culture of the migrants – mostly from Ukraine.

A similar approach was taken by a local NGO working in a mid-sized city close to Krakow. They strove to provide the space for exercising Ukrainian culture to the inhabitants of the city with a Ukrainian background. Celebrations such as Easter and St. John's Night were organised, along with artistic workshops held in Ukrainian. This was done through hiring people with Ukrainian backgrounds, who served as animators of these events. The events were conducted in Ukrainian, some of them were open to Polish participants and, if so, were conducted bilingually. The NGO also gave financial support to the acquisition of Polish language by organising a Polish language course open to all interested people who came to Poland after February 2022.

Willa Decjusza, an NGO operating in Krakow had a wide offer attracting “new Cracovians” – people of a non-Polish background settling in the city. They featured activities focused on children and available in several languages, open cultural activities oriented on the presentation of minority cultures to wider audiences, and several social and artistic projects oriented on the inclusion of minorities and cultural exchange. Around half of these projects were organised in close collaboration with members of the immigrant minorities.

The acknowledgement of the migrant minorities' presence and recognition of their culture was also performed by other public institutions and NGOs in Kraków (for instance: Open Krakow initiative, Interkulturalni, Wielokulturowy Krakow, Zustricz NGO, IB, and more). These were both public institutions, NGOs and minority organisations and all played a crucial role in providing space for engagement with both Polish culture and with the culture of migrant minorities.

It seems, therefore, that, despite the omissions in the official policy documents, the *de facto* cultural policy of Poland provides room for migrants' cultural expression, cultural exchange and a mingling of minority and mainstream cultures. However, as some experts told me, these activities flourished following the massive arrival of Ukrainians seeking shelter in Poland after February 2022. Still, while central cultural policy towards migrant minorities remains limited, local bodies – such as the city of Krakow and the Małopolska Voivodship – formulated policies of migrant minorities' inclusion in close collaboration with NGOs and civil society actors long established within the intercultural relations area. This became a policy of local governing bodies supporting financially the activities that not only brought migrants closer to the Polish language and culture (as per the central cultural policy recommendations), but also those that gave them space and possibilities to engage with their background culture, as well as those that provided cultural activities with no ethnic or national indication of their types. In this regard, the *de facto* cultural policy of Poland – even if this was the local, municipal, rather than national strategy, opened up the celebration of minority culture in various forms and with the support of public money. It also supported creating spaces for cultural co-production, though this offer was less visible than the one oriented on minority culture. Additionally, there were several commercial organisations oriented toward celebrating immigrant minority culture, from music to film and literature (See Mucha 2021). The local governing bodies, NGOs and private actors filled the gap presented by the central cultural policy, providing venues for new inhabitants with a migration background and for their cultural practices to be displayed and celebrated.

The organised activities oriented toward the cultural inclusion of migrants, though they were rarely evaluated with a focus on their effects on minorities' inclusion. There is scant knowledge regarding the question of whether this approach supports inclusion or not. This is not surprising, as these issues also present a gap in international literature on the intersection of cultural heritage and migration studies, as discussed earlier.

Norwegian Cultural Policy towards Migrating People

Norwegian cultural policy towards migrants started to be formulated as part of a general national cultural policy amid the growing influx of people to the country and the awareness of the Norwegian government that immigrants will take a permanent place in Norwegian society. In the period of interest to this analysis (2010-today), Norwegian cultural policy has evolved in particular ways. The first analysed documents, from around 2010, seemed to mostly acknowledge the fact that immigrants have now become a permanent part of society, yet their cultural participation differs significantly from the one of the overall population. Throughout the nearly two decades between 2010 and today, the governmental documents underlined the unequal participation of migrant people in institutionalised culture, stating that the percentage of those participating does not reflect their presence in society. The data from the White Paper *Visuell kunst* (2011-2012: 194) showed that migrants from the EU, US, Canada and Australia had higher rates of participation in institutionalised culture as an audience than the average Norwegian population, while those with a background in countries in Asia, Africa, South America, and Europe outside the EU – lower. Overall, the lack of representation of migrant people in the cultural sector – as performers and as audience, has been seen as problematic from the beginning of the analysed period. Initially, however, there was little focus on actual strategies to combat this unequal participation, with more efforts being put into identifying the problem. Simultaneously, the necessity to protect immigrant culture had been expressed in most documents. This protection regarded supporting their languages, but also archiving the memories of the migrants. Museums were instructed to work towards archiving and displaying the culture of immigrant minorities, aimed at making the new Norwegians able to develop knowledge about their background culture and to present their culture to the majority society to fight stereotypes.¹³ It was underlined, however, that the protection of minority cultures could not be done at the cost of the Norwegian language and culture. This stance, pictured by examples in a White Paper 2011-2012,¹⁴ is significant, as it reveals the way Norwegian and immigrant cultures were seen back then by the government. Namely, it shows that “Norwegian” and “immigrant” cultures were dichotomised. There was an opening for inspiration from and the internationalisation of Norwegian culture with the help of the culture of migrant minorities,

¹³ *Kulturredningen 2014; Kulturpolitikk fram mot 2014*

¹⁴ *Kultur, inkludering og deltaking 2011-2012*

but migrant people's culture was not seen as part of national Norwegian culture. This view changed in later documents.

Overall, at least as part of the rhetoric, the governmental documents after 2010 saw migrant people as a resource, also in terms of the richness of the Norwegian cultural scene. The governmental documents forced a notion of internationalisation of Norwegian culture through the presence and participation of immigrant artists in this culture.

The late 2010s brought a rising focus on local public institutions and organisations as the providers of cultural offerings. The White Paper 2018¹⁵ expressed the importance of local cultural institutions for providing equal access to culture for all. Local libraries and local cultural and leisure organisations were named as places providing an arena for migrants' cultural participation – both as the audience and as the performers. Additionally, organisations of migrants were valued in the White Paper 2018¹⁶ as providing arenas for integration, creation of identity and development of local belonging. This was a sign of a more specific strategy that involved practical tips on how, where and by whom the inclusion of migrant people into the cultural sector should be done. Culture was seen as an arena of “everyday integration”¹⁷ participation which was meant to acquaint migrants with Norwegian culture better. It therefore shows that the dichotomist view on migrants' and Norwegian culture was continued in the cultural policy in the late 2010s.

The vision of a flat structure of the cultural sector in Norway, prioritising local institutions and organisations, including migrant organisations, as arenas for everyday cultural participation was continued in further documents. Migrants and Norwegians of immigrant descent were supposed to become involved in the cultural life of Norway through the local institutions and organisations. Notably, the documents from the second half of the 2010s started seeing migrant minorities in a more nuanced way and beyond the reductionist, homogenising view. Migration background started to be seen as one of the aspects of individual background that might have worked as a barrier to participation in the cultural sector, rather than being an essentialised characteristic of individual holistic identity. In other words, migration background became one of the possible axes of vulnerability in a similar way that the economy, health, social and other barriers were seen. Cultural policy started targeting all these barriers to bring diversity into the

¹⁵ *Kulturens kraft 2018-2019*

¹⁶ *Frivilligheita – sterk, sjølvstendig, mangfaldig 2018-2019*

¹⁷ *Kulturens kraft 2018-2019: 71*

cultural sector, with this diversity now being regarded not only as ethnic diversity, but also as economic, social and cultural. The inclusion of people presenting these and other vulnerabilities was performed through the de-hierarchisation of the cultural sector and through providing free access points to cultural offerings in a local setting.

The White Paper 2020¹⁸ granted the right to immigrant children to participate in culture and express their culture within the mainstream cultural discourse. This right was now not connected to a quest to “internationalise” Norwegian culture and does not have the purpose of “inspirational influence.” It rather recognised migrants’ children culture as belonging to the Norwegian mainstream and hence required protection within institutionalised cultural discourse. In this regard, the dichotomist view on migrant vs. Norwegian culture changed, being replaced by the view that Norwegian culture transforms and accommodates the input of new Norwegians with immigrant backgrounds as its own. Immigrant children were expected to participate in the cultural sector as users and performers, with the flat structure policy involving widely accessible public places offering cultural activities being supposed to enhance this. It was also stated that the participation of people of immigrant backgrounds in culture should be supported by inclusive recruitment strategies to Norwegian cultural schools,¹⁹ in which people with immigrant backgrounds are underrepresented in relation to their percentage in the population. The confirmation of changing a dichotomist approach to Norwegian vs immigrant culture was expressed in the White Paper from 2023,²⁰ which recognised integration as a two-way process involving changes in the receiving society. The two most recent policy documents²¹ focused more generally on the inclusion of diverse actors in the cultural sector and the policy strategies targeted vulnerable groups overall, with no special indication of immigrants, even if migration background was recognised as one of the axes of vulnerability and access barriers.

¹⁸ *Oppløve, skape, dele 2020-21*

¹⁹ Voluntary schools featuring, usually, a one-year-long programme oriented on gaining skills in the chosen area of arts and culture (e.g. playing an instrument, dancing, signing, theatre, sculpture, painting and more). Education in culture schools is beyond the standard schooling programme and students often take a gap year in their education path to attend it.

²⁰ *Rom for deltakelse 2023-2025*

²¹ *Rom for deltakelse 2023-2025; Kunstnarkår 2022-2023*

Immigrant Minorities' Culture in Norwegian Cultural Policy – Summary of Focus Areas

Overall Norwegian Cultural Policy towards migrant minorities throughout the period 2010-2023 was characterised by the following:

- Recognition of migrant people's right to express their culture and language and the need to provide room for this expression

These statements were often acknowledged in relation to the international agreements Norway has signed. There was consent for the recognition of migrant minorities' rights, but especially at the beginning of the analysed period, the strategy to implement this right was vague. Later, immigrant children were addressed in particular as having the right to cultural expression and the strategies to execute it included participation in local cultural organisations and activities, including migrant organisations.

- Supporting migrant people's participation in the cultural sector in Norway as audience, performers and employees of cultural institutions

The policies working toward this goal included balancing power relations in the cultural sector, the flat structure of the cultural sector, prioritising local and grassroots organisations and public libraries, and granting freedom of speech regarding cultural expression.

- Archiving migrants' culture

There is an observed trend towards the heritagisation of migrant culture within the national museums and institutions, and this is also recommended in the policies.

- Recognising migrant minorities as a resource for the Norwegian cultural sector

Migrant minorities have been seen as a resource by the Norwegian cultural sector. Their presence has been formulated in the policy as a way to internationalise the Norwegian cultural sector and as an inspiration to the cultural field. Later, migrant minorities, and more specifically "immigrant children", started to be seen as active producers of the common contemporary culture of Norway.

- Viewing the cultural sector as an arena for migrant people's integration.

Integration was seen as facilitated by cultural participation – in both aspects – the migrant population getting to know Norwegian culture and presenting migrants’ culture to the mainstream to fight stereotypes. Public libraries have been seen as a core arena for local cultural participation with their free cultural offering. Local leisure organisations, including those led by members of migrant minorities, have been seen as important arenas for the development of local belonging.

Implementation of Norwegian Cultural Policy Towards Immigrant Minorities – Remarks from Ethnographic Observations in Public Cultural Institutions

Observations made in public spaces and public libraries in Norway, in the area of Oslo, proved that the libraries were indeed inclusive community spaces, open to everyone and providing visitors with various opportunities for cultural engagement. The target orientation of library activities towards migrant minorities was rare (although there were some language cafés organised specifically for migrants), but activities open to the general public attracted migrant minorities and served as a meeting point for them. The offer of books in various languages was very rich in libraries in Oslo, Drammen and Asker, both for children and for adults. The inclusion of those with vulnerabilities, which also concerned language barriers, was done in a complex way, without a separate focus on migrants. This was perhaps a positive sign, as it limited the stigmatisation of people with an immigrant background, shifting the focus from essentialised identity to language skills and various limitations regarding language acquisition. An example of this strategy is a special needs shelf in Asker library, with books tagged as written in easy Norwegian, but also as written with big letters, sign language and more (Image 1). These public institutions, therefore, rarely organised ethnically targeted events, which was in contrast to the activities seen in similar institutions (libraries) in Poland.

Image 1: Special needs shelf in Asker Library. Source: Author's archive.

When it comes to the archiving of migrant cultures in local and national museums, the Folekmuseet has been a pioneer, with annual events like Polish Christmas and Arabic Christmas organised in the past, as well as the exhibitions: *Pakistani home*, and *Norway yesterday, today, tomorrow* (Nikielska-Sekuła 2023). These attempts reflected the inclusion of minority cultures into the mainstream heritage narrations.

Minorities were also included in the ticketed cultural scene of local places in Norway – the concerts and cultural events of artists coming from the ancestral homelands of the biggest immigrant minorities in Norway were common.

Polish and Norwegian Cultural Policy and Immigrant Minorities – Conclusions

Polish and Norwegian Cultural Policies differ significantly when it comes to the place they assign to people with immigrant backgrounds concerning cultural expression. The latest Norwegian policy is to open up the mainstream Norwegian culture to the culture of immigrant minorities and grant rights, especially to children with immigrant backgrounds, to cultural expression *as part of* the mainstream Norwegian culture. The policy, therefore, supports viewing the culture of immigrant minorities as part of the mainstream Norwegian culture. This is not the case in Poland, where the policy sees migrants as needing to learn the Polish language and culture in order to *integrate into* Polish society. The rights for minority cultural expression

for immigrants were not granted and the national culture has not opened up for the inclusion of migrant minorities' cultural expressions.

This stark difference between Norwegian and Polish cultural policy, shrinks, however, at the level of implementation. As shown, the initiatives supported by the local governing bodies in Poland showcased a broad cultural offer oriented toward minorities and also provided arenas for minorities to express their culture publicly. These public expressions of culture were often done in the form of festivals, showcasing what was termed as “intercultural dialogue” (Bodo 2012; Lixinski 2023; Nikielska-Sekuła 2023). The discussed initiatives were similar to those performed in Norway, such as the Globus Festival in Drammen – where the minority culture was presented to the general public through food. Additionally, the active role of public libraries as cultural engagement arenas in the respective countries was similar. An important difference, however, was that in Norway, the cultural offer of public institutions such as libraries was addressed mainly towards the general public, and people with immigrant backgrounds could partake in them freely. Ethnography in Poland showed, on the other hand, that in addition to cultural events addressed to the mainstream, where migrant people were welcome to attend freely, there were a large number of events organised by local libraries and cultural organisations that were addressed primarily to minorities, especially from Ukraine. While they were open to the mainstream population, the way they were marked, for instance as a “Ukrainian book club”, made it less likely that the general public would participate. This potentially limited the possibilities of establishing meeting arenas for minority and majority populations as part of these encounters. However, it did acknowledge the minority's right to maintain their background cultural practices, legitimising it through public institutions. What is more, this strategy, while supporting the background cultural expression of immigrant minorities, did not directly encourage them to participate in mainstream cultural heritage.

The Polish approach, therefore, targeted specifically the minority groups, even if the event remained open to anyone, while the Norwegian approach targeted the general population and strived to include immigrants within it. In both countries, there were institutional events that legitimised minority culture through their display in public institutions.

Getting to Know Cultural Heritage Participation Patterns

The types of participation in cultural heritage presented below were formulated inductively, based on the findings obtained through qualitative analyses presented elsewhere²² and in a way, that accurately depicts the cultural participation modes of the respondents. The types encompass three dimensions, each with several categories, and while each category within these dimensions was represented by some respondents, not every combination of dimensions' categories was present.

The types of participation in cultural heritage by respondents were built on the information obtained during interviews. Instead of focusing on pre-conceptualised ideas of cultural heritage, the focus in the interviews was placed on individual practices regarding cultural heritage and the places people associate these heritage performances, or elements of them, with (see: Çağlar & Glick Schiller 2018). This further allowed me to conceptualise cultural heritage participation types beyond methodological nationalism (Wimmer & Glick Schiller 2002) and with acknowledgement of the actual continuation or change of practices between localities, rather than focusing on tracing the essentialised origin of cultural heritage performances discussed. Even though the respondents themselves very often classified their engagement in cultural heritage as reflecting “Polish”, “Norwegian”, or “Ukrainian” practices, I found that they used these ethnonationalist characteristics as synonymous with the local habitus in respective countries. Following this reasoning, the patterns of participation in cultural heritage were conceptualised concerning the three dimensions I describe below: **type**, **characteristic** and **motivation**. These dimensions focus solely on the practices exercised *after* relocation to the new homeland in temporal terms. Therefore, practices followed upon visits to the ancestral homelands, or elsewhere, during travels after relocation are also taken into consideration in order to acknowledge the translocality (Greiner & Sakdapolrak 2013) of the respondents' livelihoods.

The first level of identification of cultural heritage participation patterns strives to describe the individual combination of “brought” and “acquired” practices in the respondents' engagement with cultural heritage after relocation. It is referred to as **type**. It focuses on the practices around cultural heritage performed after the settlement in the new homeland and describes (1) the

²² A forthcoming publication from the project with a working title: “Cultural heritage participation patterns among immigrants.”

continuation of the cultural practices from the local habitus in the ancestral homeland, (2) the engagement in the cultural practices encountered in the new homeland, (3) the creation of possible hybrid practices, through inspiration by the local habitus in the new and ancestral homeland. I divide the type into four sub-categories: (a) integrational (engaging with both ancestral and new homeland heritage), (b) assimilationist (engaging with new homeland heritage only), (c) separative (engaging with ancestral homeland heritage only) and (d) marginalised (rejecting both ancestral and new homeland heritage).

The second dimension of identification regards the definitional order the respondents referred to when describing their cultural practices/engagement with cultural heritage. I call it **characteristics**. I distinguish here among (a) ethnonational order (referring to ethnic and/or national labels in describing heritage practices, with sub-categories: hybrid, ancestral homeland, new homeland), (b) individualistic order (referring to heritage practices as individual), (c) familial order (referring to heritage practices as connected to one's family); and (d) cosmopolitan order (referring to heritage practices as deriving from global and cosmopolitan orders). In view of some respondents, their heritage was oriented on their individual way of making certain traditions, and this was honoured in the categorisation, even though broader traditions the individual heritage performances were derived from might refer to other orders.

The final aspect assessed was the **motivation** to engage in cultural heritage practices, where I distinguished between (a) internal and (b) external motivation. The aim was to express the difference in participating in certain cultural practices due to one's own will, or because of structural coercion.

	Dimensions	Categories and Sub-categories	Description
Cultural heritage participation patterns	Type	<i>Do people break or continue with pre-migration heritage practices? Do they engage with new practices post-migration?</i>	
		Integrational	engaging with both ancestral and new homeland heritage
		Assimilationist	engaging with new homeland heritage only
		Separative	engaging with ancestral homeland heritage only
		Marginalised	rejecting both ancestral and new homeland heritage
	Characteristics	<i>How do people define their cultural heritage practices?</i>	
		Ethnonational order	referring to ethnic and/or national labels in describing heritage practices, with three sub-categories
		✓ Hybrid	✓ referring to mixing ancestral and new homeland practices
		✓ Ancestral homeland	✓ referring to ancestral homeland practices only
		✓ New homeland	✓ referring to new homeland practices only
		Individualistic order	referring to heritage practices as individual
		Familial order	referring to heritage practices as connected to one's family
		Cosmopolitan order	referring to heritage practices as deriving from global and cosmopolitan orders
	Motivation	<i>Why do people engage with cultural heritage practices?</i>	
		Internal	participating at one's own will
External		participating due to structural coercion	

Figure 1 Cultural Heritage Participation Patterns Model

Cultural Heritage Participation Patterns: Distribution in the Researched Population

Cultural Heritage Participation Patterns: Type, Characteristics and Motivation

This section presents the distribution of the researched population across categories within the separate dimensions of cultural heritage participation patterns.

Type

When it comes to the type of cultural heritage engagement, the majority of the respondents (65 people – 63%) represented the Integrational type. This was followed by Separative (28 – 27%). Assimilationist and Marginalised were represented only by 3.9% of the respondents for each type (4 respondents each, Table 1). When applying a division between countries (Poles in

Norway vs Ukrainians in Poland,²³ Table 2), the order of frequencies was kept, yet the numbers of respondents falling into each category indicated that the overwhelming majority of the Poles in Norway represented the Integrational type, while Ukrainians in Poland were also more than twice as numerous in the Separative type as the Poles in Norway were.

Table 1. Distribution of types.

Distribution of types		
Type	Frequency	Percentage
No data	2	1.9
Integrational	65	63.1
Assimilationist	4	3.9
Separative	28	27.2
Marginalised	4	3.9
Total	103	100

Table 2. Type by country of settlement.

Type by country of settlement			
Type	Country of settlement		
	Norway	Poland	Total
No data	1	1	2
Integrational	38	27	65
Assimilationist	4	0	4
Separative	9	19	28
Marginalised	1	3	4
Total	53	50	103

Characteristics

The majority of the respondents described their heritage practices in relation to the ethnonational order. This was followed by defining them as familial. The individualistic and cosmopolitan orders were much less popular (Table 3). Among Poles in Norway, the majority

²³ Whenever the analysis says “Poles in Norway” and “Ukrainians in Poland” it refers only to the participants of the study with that background, unless indicated otherwise.

of the respondents described their practices as Polish-Norwegian representing the ethnonational-hybrid category. Ukrainians in Poland, in turn, rather characterised their practices either as Ukrainian (ethnonational-ancestral homeland category) or as familial. This was followed by ethnonational-hybrid (the number of Ukrainians in Poland in this category was less than a third compared to Poles in Norway, Table 4).

Table 3. Distribution of characteristics.

Distribution of characteristics		
Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage
No data	2	1.9
Cosmopolitan	5	4.9
Ethnonational	70	68
Individualistic	7	6.8
Familial	19	18.4
Total	103	100

Table 4. Extended characteristics by country of settlement.

Extended characteristics by country of settlement			
Extended characteristics	Country of settlement		
	Norway	Poland	Total
Cosmopolitan	2	3	5
Ethnonational: new homeland	3	1	4
Ethnonational: ancestral homeland	9	17	26
Ethnonational: hybrid	31	9	40
Individualistic	2	5	7
Familial	5	14	19
Total	52	49	101

Overall, more Poles in Norway than Ukrainians in Poland identified their cultural heritage as referring to the ethnonational order. On the other hand, more Ukrainians in Poland than Poles in Norway referred to familial characteristics when describing their heritage practices. The reason behind this, as observed qualitatively in the interviews, was a relatively weaker national identification of Ukrainian respondents compared to the Poles. A common answer of a Polish-

Norwegian respondent to the question “Who are you?” was – “I am a Pole”, while in the case of Ukrainian respondents, their answers often encompassed various identifications connected to gender, family role and occupation. National identification was rather named as one of the aspects of their identity. In other words, Ukrainians, while still identifying with the country of origin, were more prone to prioritise their family-related identifications, while Poles in Norway primarily identified with their Polish ethnic origin, even if this was accompanied by other parallel identifications, and nuanced with the identifications referring to the membership in Norwegian mainstream society.

Motivation

An overwhelming majority of the respondents expressed an internal motivation to engage with heritage practices (over 88%, Table 5). Interestingly, the only ones who admitted to an external motivation were Poles in Norway (Table 6). In Norway, the pressure on people with migration backgrounds to become involved in mainstream heritage practices is quite high, especially for those having children – there is, for instance, an expectation to participate in school-organised heritage activities, such as Norwegian Constitution Day and Christmas Celebrations. In Poland, this pressure is lower, even for the mainstream population. What is more, many national heritage events are connected to religion and are voluntary, while being a non-Catholic, as is the case for many Ukrainians in Poland, is a legitimate excuse to abstain from participation. Poles in Norway also had, on average, more children and in qualitative interviews admitted that the heritage they engage with is often motivated exactly by having children. More specifically, they named here the participation in heritage activities through school, but also a will to pass on traditions from Poland through observing Polish traditions at home, and these activities were sometimes motivated externally.

Table 5. Distribution of motivation.

Distribution of motivation		
Motivation	Frequency	Percentage
No data	2	1.9
Internal	91	88.3
External	10	9.7
Total	103	100

Table 6. Motivation by country of settlement.

Motivation by country of settlement			
Motivation	Country of settlement		
	Norway	Poland	Total
No data	1	1	2
Internal	42	49	91
External	10	0	10
Total	53	50	103

Three-dimensional cultural heritage participation patterns

The three dimensions of the typology were combined and as a result, three-dimensional cultural heritage participation patterns were created. Each respondent was classified as belonging to one category of the three-dimensional typology. Categories that had low frequencies were cut off. There were 84 observations remaining, distributed across six categories. Table 7 below presents the three-dimensional typology with observations that are higher than seven.

Table 7. Distribution of three-dimensional heritage participation patterns.

Distribution of the three-dimensional heritage participation patterns		
Three-dimensional heritage participation patterns	Frequency	Percentage
Integrational-Ethnonational: hybrid-Internal	33	32
Separative-Ethnonational: ancestral homeland-Internal	14	13.6
Integrational-Ethnonational: ancestral homeland-Internal	11	10.7
Separative-Familial-Internal	11	10.7
Integrational-Familial-Internal	8	7.8
Integrational-Ethnonational: hybrid-External	7	6.8
Total	84	81.4
Excluded	19	18.4
Total (with excluded cases)	103	100

When the three-dimensional cultural heritage participation patterns were divided into the countries of settlement (Table 8), it became clear that the Poles in Norway overpopulated the categories Integrational – Ethnonational: hybrid, with both motivations: Internal and External. Over 70% of Poles in Norway acquired new homeland practices and sustained practices brought from their ancestral homeland referring to their overall heritage practices as Polish-Norwegian or both – Polish *and* Norwegian. Ukrainians in Poland, in turn, were more evenly distributed across all categories with internal motivation to maintain heritage practices.

To shed light on possible reasons behind the spread of respondents across the categories of cultural heritage participation patterns, both qualitative and quantitative analyses were employed. Qualitative analyses aimed to explain the reasoning behind the belonging to various categories based on the qualitative interviews, quantitative analyses, in turn, were aimed at determining the variables that might have influenced the probability of falling into subsequent categories with statistical significance. In other words, the quantitative analyses – the correlation and logistic regression – were supported by the findings from qualitative interviews and observations.

After correlating the three-dimensional typology with the background characteristics of the respondents and running the logistic regression to measure the probability of falling into each category of the three-dimensional cultural heritage participation patterns, the results were assessed against the information coming from the qualitative interviews. Based on this two-step

mixed-methods analysis, significant categories that might have influenced the typology were indicated. The first and the most striking one was the country of settlement, and its influence was already indicated above. I discuss it in more detail below. Subsequently, I discuss the remaining variables that might have influenced the heritage participation patterns.

Table 8. Distribution of cultural heritage participation types in Poland and Norway.

Distribution of cultural heritage participation types in Poland and Norway			
Cultural Heritage Participation Type	Country of settlement		
	Norway	Poland	Total
Integrational-Ethnonational: hybrid-Internal	24	9	33
	54.5%	22.5%	39.3%
Separative-Ethnonational: ancestral homeland-Internal	5	9	14
	11.4%	22.5%	16.7%
Integrational-Ethnonational: ancestral homeland-Internal	3	8	11
	6.8%	20%	13.1%
Separative-Familial-Internal	3	8	11
	6.8%	20%	13.1%
Integrational-Familial-Internal	2	6	8
	4.5%	15%	9.5%
Integrational-Ethnonational: hybrid-External	7	0	7
	15.9%	0%	8.3%
Total	44	40	84
	100%	100%	100%

Country of Settlement

The country of settlement correlated with three-dimensional cultural heritage participation patterns and this relationship was statistically significant with a moderate strength (V Cramer coefficient, value 0.504, statistical significance 0.001). As said, Poles in Norway were quite homogeneous when it came to cultural heritage participation patterns representing *Integrational-ethnonational: hybrid-internal* and *external* patterns. They were overall more prone to engage with heritage due to external motivation. Ukrainian respondents, on the other hand, were displayed more evenly across the categories with internal motivation. They were

more likely to belong to the *Integrational-ethnonational: ancestral homeland-internal* category than Poles in Norway were. Overall, less engagement in heritage defined as new-homeland ethnonational among Ukrainians in Poland than among Poles in Norway was observed. Ukrainians in Poland were also far less likely to represent the *Integrational-Ethnonational: hybrid-internal* category. As said, respective samples in the two countries were similarly differentiated when it comes to their core characteristics (age, labour market participation, education level, gender division and mainstream language level), I would therefore lean towards attributing the differences in the distribution across participation types categories to cultural policies in the respective countries of settlement. A stronger cultural policy towards minorities in Norway might have influenced crowding *Integrational – ethnonational: hybrid (internal and external)* patterns by Poles in Norway. On the other hand, the rather even differentiation in relation to the distribution across categories among the Ukrainians in Poland may indicate a prevailing significance of individual choices of people regarding heritage engagement over the country-specific policy impact. Moreover, Ukrainians in Poland were more often represented by the separative type, even though the majority of them still fell into an integrational one. Several factors might have played a role here. The specific nature of the Polish cultural policy towards migrants, which at the implementation level promotes minority culture, rather than working towards the inclusion of migrants in the mainstream cultural practices, could have influenced the findings. I discuss the possible ways in which the cultural policies of Norway and Poland could have influenced the cultural participation types in the discussion and conclusions section. Another explanation might relate to the shorter length of stay in the new country among Ukrainians in Poland compared to the Poles in Norway – especially regarding women. I discuss this in the next paragraph, together with other variables. Moreover, familial characteristics of heritage across various types were more common among the Ukrainians in Poland than among Poles in Norway. As already signalled, this can be attributed to the fact that nationalism and national identity are well-established in Polish society, which was reflected in the narrations of the respondents. The national identity of Ukrainian respondents, in turn, was presented as one of several aspects of identity, usually coming after gender and familial identifications. Qualitative interviews showed clearly that for some respondents the war events had intensified their engagement with their Ukrainian heritage, though many still defined their heritage practices as coming from familial, rather than national traditions.

While gender alone did not significantly influence the cultural heritage participation patterns, the combination of gender and settlement country (Table 9) was found to play a role in shaping

the distribution of the respondents across categories, yet it was not statistically significant. Polish women in Norway were represented mostly by pattern *integrational-ethnonational: hybrid-external and internal*, while if the respondents settled in Norway fell into a separatist type these were more often men than women. On the contrary, in Poland, Ukrainian women were mostly represented by separative types, while men more often fell into patterns that were integrational. This is interesting and requires a qualitative exploration, as the sample divided into gender and country is too small to run meaningful statistical analyses. Ukrainian women in Poland had a shorter length of stay than the rest of the sample (see Table 9), eight of them were temporary protection beneficiaries who arrived after February 2022 and were still learning the language. They differed from the rest of the sample by the type of migration (forced), shorter length of stay and language acquisition being still at the beginning of the process. Six of them represented the separative type, with variations regarding characteristics – *cosmopolitan, ancestral homeland* and *familial*. The remaining two were *integrational ancestral homeland* and *integrational familial* (all with internal motivation). The two women representing integrational types were both still learning Polish, one worked and the other one did not. What differentiated them from the rest of the subsample of women who arrived after February 2022 was having children. Women representing the separative type did not have school-age children (five had no children at all, and one had an adult daughter). The two remaining women that represented the integrational type had subsequently four and two children of school age. It therefore seems that having children might have worked as a shortcut to engaging with new heritage practices in Poland, which helped overcome vulnerabilities coming from the length of stay, and language skills.

On the contrary, in Norway, while the separatist type was not that popular, if represented at all, it was more common to be represented by men. Men in Poland, in turn, were much more often representing the integrational types. The differences between the male respondents in Norway and in Poland are not significant, besides the command of language. While the overwhelming majority of Ukrainian male respondents in Poland (11 out of 13 - 84%) stated they had a very good command of Polish, less than half of the male respondents in Norway admitted a fluent command of Norwegian (5 out of 12 – 41%). The command of language was statistically significant (V Cramer coefficient with value 0.329 and statistical significance 0.014) when correlated with the three-dimensional typology, yet the relationship was rather weak. Qualitative analyses showed that males from Poland who settled in Norway and represented the separative type often had a fluent or very good command of Norwegian, so this is not the

explanatory factor. The majority of males in Norway had partners and children that were living with them in Norway. Two of those who did not have a partner, or whose partner lived in Poland represented the separative type. This is too little evidence to conclude that singles and those with immediate families (partners and children) left behind in Poland engaged with the heritage of a new homeland less often. Neither the length of stay, the job status, nor having or not having children differentiated males in Norway regarding their cultural heritage participation patterns.

Table 9. Length of stay in the country of settlement (in years).

Length of stay in the country of settlement (in years)				
Gender	Country of settlement	Mean	Count	Standard deviation
Female	Norway	9.39	41	5.607
	Poland	5.49	37	4.080
Male	Norway	9.75	12	2.958
	Poland	8.38	13	6.886

Other Variables

Besides the country of settlement and the combination of gender and the country of settlement described above (Table 9), there were also other variables that might have influenced the cultural participation patterns in the sample. The average number of children was the highest in the categories *integrational-ethnonational: hybrid-internal* and *external*. It was followed by *Integrational-ethnonational: ancestral homeland – internal*. Those representing the *Separative-ethnonational: ancestral homeland-internal* category had the lowest number of children (Table 10). Engagement with new homeland heritage practices of those who had children was confirmed qualitatively – people with children in local schools commonly participated in local cultural celebrations for children, some of which were obligatory, some others voluntary, but customary and induced by social pressure. This was already mentioned in a previous section and it is confirmed as true independently of the country of settlement.

Table 10. Average number of children by participation type.

Average number of children by participation type	
Participation type	Average number of children
Integrational-Ethnonational: hybrid-External	1.6
Integrational-Ethnonational: hybrid-Internal	1
Integrational-Ethnonational: ancestral homeland-Internal	0.9
Integrational-Familial-Internal	0.5
Separative-Familial-Internal	0.5
Separative-Ethnonational: ancestral homeland-Internal	0.3

When not divided into gender and country of settlement, a command of the language of the mainstream country was also important. Those fluent in the mainstream language were more likely to represent the *integrational-ethnonational-hybrid internal and external* type. The majority (53%) of those who spoke the mainstream language fluently fell into *integrational-ethnonational: hybrid-internal and external* categories. To these two categories belonged also 58% of those who planned to apply for citizenship in the country of settlement and 56% of those who already had such citizenship.

Finally, the three-dimensional patterns of heritage participation correlated with the self-identification of the respondents (significance level: 0.001) and this relationship was of medium strength. The majority of people whose participation patterns were *integrational-familial* and *integrational, ethnonational: hybrid* with various motivations were self-identifying with both ancestral and new homeland. Representatives of *Separative-ethnonational: ancestral homeland* and *separative-familial* patterns as well as *Integrational-ethnonational: ancestral homeland* were most often identifying with the ancestral homeland. It confirms that cultural heritage participation is indeed closely connected to people's identity (Macdonald 2013), and hence is important and worth analysis within the broader research on migration processes.

Discussion and Conclusions

It is important to note that the heritage participation patterns are influenced by several factors connected with local and national identity, individual background, socio-cultural and economic positionality and more, as discussed above. In this section, without undermining the influence

of an individual background on the cultural heritage participation patterns, I theorise how the modes of participation in cultural heritage in the respective settlement countries could have been influenced by the Polish and Norwegian approach to immigrant culture in the national cultural policies.

As shown, more Ukrainians in Poland than Poles in Norway presented a Separative type of engagement in cultural heritage. Additionally, there was overall less engagement with heritage considered as new-homeland ethnic by Ukrainian respondents in Poland than among Polish respondents in Norway (represented mostly by a hybrid characteristic). It means that Ukrainian respondents more often refrained from engaging with the cultural heritage practices encountered in the new homeland than Poles in Norway did. What is more, they more often described their heritage as relating to the ancestral homeland ethnonational and familial orders. On the other hand, the integrational type of engagement was the most popular among Ukrainians in Poland, even though the percentage of the respondents representing it was lower than among Poles in Norway. Overall, Ukrainians in Poland were quite evenly distributed across integrational and separative types combined with ethnonational and familial characteristics, while Poles in Norway concentrated within *Integrational-ethnonational: hybrid* type.

Relating it to the assumptions of Polish cultural policy on a normative level, which suggests that migrants settling in Poland should acquire knowledge and skills in the Polish language and culture – and hence potentially the capability – to engage with Polish heritage, we may conclude that this was not really achieved – the respondents with hybrid heritage characteristic among Ukrainians in Poland were not very numerous, and the sole new-homeland orientations were scarce. When we look at the implementation of cultural policy in the form of events addressed to minorities in Poland, however, we may find some connections. A common formula of organising cultural events addressed towards minorities and focused on featuring minority culture and supporting it, and perhaps the intensity of such events addressing specifically Ukrainians in Poland after the Russian full-scale invasion of their country in 2022, might have potentially oriented Ukrainian respondents towards their culture of origin more than to the mainstream Polish culture. A branch of events addressed to both the migrants in Poland, without any indication of their ethnic origin, and the mainstream population, were often not exactly referring to specific Polish heritage, and when they were, these events were less common than

those oriented on the background culture of the migrants, and here I mostly mean Ukrainian culture.

On the other hand, Poles in Norway overrepresented the integrational-hybrid approaches. External motivation to partake in cultural heritage was solely presented by Poles in Norway. This may be explained by the structural pressure on migrants to engage with Norwegian cultural heritage also through educational institutions of children and the overall stronger policy oriented towards migrants' inclusion within the mainstream cultural heritage. Additionally, the ethnically profiled events were not often organised by public institutions (with Polish Christmas in the museum being one of the exceptions). Polish respondents in Norway were characterised by more than twice as many children on average than Ukrainians in Poland. The official Norwegian cultural policy targets migrant children in particular, and this could have impacted indirectly their parents' engagement with heritage. As already stated, participation in Norwegian heritage through child-oriented activities and schools and beyond was indicated by respondents both in Poland and Norway.

The main conclusion stemming from this analysis is that the cultural heritage participation patterns, while influenced by respondents' individual approach to heritage performance and connected to some of their background characteristics, are shaped by the cultural policy of the country of settlement. A strong cultural policy may induce a sort of unification of cultural heritage participation patterns, as happened for the Poles in Norway, while a weaker cultural policy differentiates patterns of cultural heritage participation among migrants allowing for a greater impact of their individual backgrounds and personal orientations. Having children in the education system, who are exposed to the mainstream cultural heritage practices, influences the engagement of the adults, even though they are not directly targeted by heritage activities organised by educational institutions. Additionally, language has proved to be, to some extent, a barrier to the engagement in cultural heritage encountered in the new homeland. Finally, the length of stay influenced the way people engaged with heritage.

These factors influencing engagement with heritage leads to the conclusion that it is possible to identify preferred cultural heritage participation patterns and design strong policies targeting not only migrants, but also their children, in order to induce certain ways of engagement with heritage by the migrants.

Cultural Heritage Participation Patterns and Emplacement

This section presents the index of emplacement created for the purpose of this research project, the distribution of its values in the researched population, as well as the findings from correlations of the index with the cultural heritage participation types. The section therefore answers the question of whether the emplacement process is related to cultural heritage participation patterns.

Emplacement Index

Emplacement is the process of getting settled post-migration in a new locality. It was theorised by Çağlar and Glick-Schiller (Glick Schiller & Çağlar 2013; 2016; Çağlar & Glick Schiller 2018) and suggested as useful in addressing some shortcomings of the concept of integration in migration studies. Emplacement refers to “a person’s efforts, within the barriers and opportunities that contingencies of local place-making offer, to build a life within networks of local, national, supranational, and global interconnections” (Çağlar & Glick Schiller 2018: 20–21).

Emplacement as a lens to look at the settlement process of those who migrate to new destinations takes into account the spatiality (and locality) of human life, but also acknowledges the entanglement of locality into multiscalar processes and “explores the processes of the mutual constitution of the local, regional, national and global through time and in the construction of social space” (Çağlar & Glick Schiller 2015: 2). Place, therefore, is shaped by relations of power coming from global, regional, national and local sources and hence *emplacement* also depends on these constellations of power shaping local formal and informal social structures.

Emplacement was seen by Çağlar and Glick Schiller as a way to talk about the adjustment of people who migrate to new localities beyond the problems and controversies that the concepts such as integration, assimilation and social cohesion raise (Çağlar & Glick Schiller 2015: 6). These controversies regard the assumption that migrants arrive in societies where the mainstream is represented by a homogeneous native population to which they should adapt. This view is no longer relevant in the context of what is known as “new migrations”, especially to localisations characterised by super-diversity (Wessendorf & Phillimore 2019). Overall, the debate around the concepts of integration and assimilation has raised multiple problems

regarding the attempts to measure the integration of those who migrate, though new solutions, while emerging, are still far from being established in the field.

With this in mind, and to answer the question of whether certain types of engagement with cultural heritage by those who migrate connect or correlate with the progress of the emplacement process, HerInt takes up the difficult task of producing **an index of emplacement** that aims to quantify the settlement progress of those who migrate in terms of adapting to the multiscale structures of the new localities of settlement.

A starting point for the emplacement index used here is the concept of a place as a meaningful arena for the postmigration settling of people. The multiscale nature of the place is acknowledged and relates to various hierarchies of power that shape social relations in particular places and that come from various scales including at neighbourhood, city, regional, national and global levels. If it is accepted that the social life in the place is influenced by multiscale structures of power that further shape the position and livelihoods of people inhabiting the place, we may conclude that adapting to these structures is crucial for successfully settling in a new location. Furthermore, the extent of this adaptation – and its success – may relate to the degree of effective emplacement.

The emplacement process, as understood here, encompasses the adaptation to local structures of the labour market, civic rights, education and socio-cultural structures, including local social networks and local cultural events addressed to the general public. Developing the ties within the structural scales of the new location of settlement, such as securing a job and/or participating in educational structures, supports settling in the new location through embeddedness into the social, cultural and economic structures of the settlement location. This is further supported by obtaining civic rights such as citizenship. Education and labour market participation were confirmed as important for people who migrate to establish postmigration adaptation to the new place (Phillimore & Goodson 2008). Adaptation to local social structures of the new settlement destination has also been recognised as an important factor of emplacement. Traditional integration literature has focused primarily on the contacts between the migrants and the natives of the receiving society as an indicator of “integration” (de Haas & Fokkema 2011). Later studies proved that embeddedness in local social structures can be successfully achieved through belonging and identifying with various local communities, including those oriented on minority identifications, provided that their activity and existence is established as part of the local social fabric (Nikielska-Sekuła 2018; see also Bivand Erdal & Oeppen 2013: 871).

Following this, the development of local identifications and belonging to the localities of settlement is also seen here as meaningful for the process of emplacement. Local identifications include identifying with the mainstream native population, but they also constitute identifications that relate to various locally rooted positionalities: being a parent of a local school child, being an inhabitant of a certain neighbourhood, a worker at a certain company with local offices, or a member of a local ethnic community. They may foster emplacement in local structures beyond methodological nationalism (Wimmer & Glick Schiller 2002). This was discussed theoretically by Anthias (2008) and operationalised as translocational positionality, though also exemplified empirically by scholars (Fangen 2006a; 2006b; 2007; Nikielska-Sekuła 2018). Furthermore, a self-assessment of both the progress of individual emplacement and the perceived acceptance by local communities in the new settlement destination helps grasp the progress of emplacement as seen by an individual, allowing to highlight the actor's perspective on their position within the formal and informal structures of the new settlement locality.

The indicators of emplacement presented above were chosen as relevant for the population in question and I further explain how they were incorporated in the emplacement index. It is important to note that these indicators are connected to the power positionalities of the localities of settlement, along with the barriers and opportunities found there by individuals. Addressing them is useful in research oriented on emplacement in the context of policies. The current research, however, focuses on cultural participation patterns approached in an individualistic way and aims to answer the question of whether there is a relationship between individual emplacement and participation in cultural heritage. For this reason, the power positionalities of places, along with the emplacement barriers the locality presents, are not directly involved in the index, which focuses on the outcomes, range and progress of the emplacement process of the respondents at the time of the interview. However, when possible and relevant for the shape of cultural heritage participation patterns, the local structures, acting both as limits and opportunities for heritage engagement, were discussed in a previous section.

The emplacement index consists of two main dimensions: structural and socio-cultural.

Structural emplacement regards various manners of people's participation in the formal structures, usually produced by the regional and national authorities of the receiving society. This participation further enhances emplacement in the new locality and works equally for migrant and non-migrant populations, although in this study we are only interested in people

who have a direct migration experience. The formal structures one adjusts to, which might enhance successful settling in the new place and are of interest here, include the labour market, education, and citizenship. The index collates information about the labour market participation of the respondents – whether they work and, if so, whether their job status reflects their professional education, is lower or higher – as studies show that working below one’s qualification negatively influences the view of successful settlement in the eyes of mobile people (Phillimore & Goodson 2008). Moreover, the index looks at the respondents’ involvement in educational institutions in the receiving society – from language courses, short professional courses and schooling to academic education. The reason behind it is that participation in various forms of education fosters emplacement through acquiring both social and cultural habitus in the new location – more salient in relation to primary, secondary and high schools and universities, but also true for shorter courses and even language courses.²⁴ Finally, the index is interested in the citizenship practices of the actors – whether they have obtained citizenship of the new country and, if not, whether they plan to do so, or they would do so if they were able. Access to rights connected to citizenship is seen as an important factor of emplacement into macro-scales of the new location.

Socio-cultural emplacement is looked at here from several angles. It focuses on establishing local social ties, belonging to the new localities of settlement, the perceived level of acceptance (of a person and their cultural practices) by the local community, and self-evaluation of integration – an important evaluation factor showing how the actors’ see their own progress in the emplacement process. Additionally, the index is also interested in the adaptation to public cultural life in new localities – its local structures and participation in cultural events. The sociocultural emplacement index follows the three-dimensional structure: social, identificational, and cultural focusing on:

1. Emplacement through social embedding in the new locality

Here, the focus is on establishing social ties in the location of settlement. The orientation here is not on the contacts specifically with the majority society, but on establishing social ties within the new location (maintained offline but also online – but connected to the locality of

²⁴ It is clear that some respondents, e.g. highly skilled professionals, may not need to participate in formal education postmigration beyond language courses and as a matter of fact, the majority of HerInt respondents did not do so. Still, those who did, because they arrived before completing their studies in their old country or out of other reasons, showed a greater understanding of local sociocultural structures and better embeddedness into them.

settlement) and the range of these social ties – whether they span across various groups in the new locality – friends circle, work and neighbourhood related ties etc, or whether they are limited e.g. to close family members. Hence, it is not the ethnic nature of these social relations that suggests the progress of emplacement, but rather the multiplicity of various ties developed across formal and informal social structures in the new locality, or a scarcity of them. One of the factors included here is marriage or a relationship with a person met in a new location.

2. Identification with groups/collectivities/communities in the receiving society and belonging to the new locations (felt and perceived)

The emplacement in local structures on a micro level of personal identification is of focus here. Do the respondents identify with any groups located in the place of settlement? If so, are there a few or several such groups? Does their self-identification include identifications embedded in the new homeland's local structures (local parents group, attendees of a language course, workers of a local company, as well as the ethnic minority group in the new locality) or relates to the external identifications (such as general national identifications not connected to the new locality, identifications with global groups such as music fans). Does the new location feel like home on the level of operationalisation? In this dimension of the emplacement index, the transnational turn in migration studies (Faist 2004) is taken into account, assuming that feeling at home in several transnational locations does not diminish emplacement in a particular location, as long as one feels at home there. The multiplicity of local identifications – again not oriented on ethnicity, but rather on becoming comfortable and developing a sense of belonging to the place through identification that is embedded locally, is of focus here. Finally, the perceived feeling of acceptance of individual cultural practices locally is of interest here. The individual assessment of the way others in the local structures see the respondent and their everyday cultural practices is seen as important in the emplacement process as it may legitimise the respondents' feeling of belonging or diminish it.

3. Language acquisition and participation in cultural events in the receiving society

Local structures of the settlement place are influenced by cultural characteristics. In the case of both Poland and Norway, the public spaces and formal structures of the society are dominated by the mainstream dominant languages – Polish and Norwegian respectively. Acquiring skills in these respective languages facilitates moving around and along the local sociocultural fabric on micro, meso and macro levels. Adaptation to the cultural structure of the locality in its

linguistic aspect is therefore of interest here. Another aspect of interest is participation in local public culture, signalling an embedding in local structures of cultural life. The assumption is that participation in mainstream events open for everyone shows a greater range of emplacement processes than participation in closed events for smaller, designated groups, yet the latter is also a sign of progressing emplacement.

Since the emplacement index is correlated with cultural heritage participation patterns, it is important to note that the cultural indicators in the index presented above *were not involved* in the creation of cultural heritage participation patterns. Participation in the cultural events in the new locality is differentiated from individual heritage practices of respondents that were included in assessing the heritage participation patterns.

Both dimensions of the index – structural and socio-cultural – feature three categories each (six in total). For the structural dimension, these are participation in the labour market, education and citizenship. For the sociocultural dimension, the categories are social ties in the locality of settlement, identification and belonging, and cultural adaptation. Each category is standardised based on the sum of scores gained in individual questions under each subcategory, the final score will be transformed into a value between 0 and 1 for each of the six subcategories, resulting in a joint emplacement index ranging between values 0-6. The value can be summed on each of the two dimensions of the index separately (structural and socio-cultural, 0-3 values each) or jointly (0-6 values). In other words, the scores can be summed or analysed distinctively. The index is presented in Appendix 2.

Emplacement Index in the Sample

The joint emplacement index ranged between values 0-6. The majority of the respondents were placed around the value of 3 on the joint index (0-6p) with an average of 2.84 (Chart 3). The majority of the respondents also placed themselves between values 2 and 4. When divided into the two dimensions of the index (scale 0-3 each) – the average socio-cultural dimension was 1.51 (Chart 1), and the structural 1.34 (Chart 2).

Chart 1. Frequency distribution of the sociocultural emplacement index

Chart 2. Frequency distribution of the structural emplacement index

Chart 3. Frequency distribution of the full emplacement index

To identify significant background characteristics that influenced the index, the full index was divided into two ranges (the first between 0 and >3, and the second between 3 and 6). The frequencies at the subsequent ranges were rather evenly distributed among the genders, but with males scoring slightly higher than females (Table 11).

Table 11. Gender distribution across index ranges.

		Gender	
		Female	Male
Index ranges	0 to 3	56.4%	52.0%
	3 to 6	43.6%	48.0%

Overall, more Ukrainians in Poland scored over 3 on the index than Poles in Norway did (Table 12). What is more, the length of stay also seemed important, as those with scores over 3 had been settled in the new homeland longer (approx. three years longer, Table 13)

Table 12. Nationality distribution across index ranges.

		Nationality	
		Ukrainians	Poles
Index ranges	0 to 3	44.0%	66.0%
	3 to 6	56.5%	34.0%

Table 13. Average length of stay in the new country across index ranges.

		Mean	Count	Standard deviation
Index ranges	0 to 3	6.60	57	4.057
	3 to 6	9.52	46	6.207
Total		7.90	103	5.307

Relationship Between the Emplacement Index and Cultural Heritage Participation Types

The correlation between the three-dimensional cultural heritage participation patterns and the emplacement index was rather limited. No statistically significant relationship between the variables was observed. When correlation was applied to the two-dimensional types, combining the type (Integrational, Separative, Assimilationist, Marginalised) with narrow characteristics without subcategories (Familiar, Ethnonational, Cosmopolitan, Individual), the values were close to statistical significance, but still not significant on the level 0.05. According to these analyses, the type Integrational: Familial had the highest average score on the emplacement index, while the Separative: Ethnonational type scored the lowest – the findings, however, were not statistically significant.

This, unfortunately, does not say enough to draw conclusions, especially as the ethnonational characteristics, when not divided into subcategories, bring together both practices associated solely with the ancestral and new homeland, as well as hybrid approaches. Table 14 presents the average scores on a joint emplacement index for each three-dimensional type.

Table 14. Joint emplacement index and the three-dimensional Cultural Heritage participation Patterns

Parameter (three-dimensional cultural heritage participation patterns)	Posterior			95% Credible Interval	
	Mode	Mean	Variance	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Integrational- Ethnonational: hybrid-Internal	3.056	3.056	0.021	2.770	3.343
Separative- Ethnonational: ancestral homeland- Internal	2.473	2.473	0.050	2.034	2.913
Integrational- Ethnonational: ancestral homeland- Internal	2.760	2.760	0.064	2.264	3.255
Separative-Familial- Internal	2.567	2.567	0.064	2.071	3.063
Integrational- Familial-Internal	3.132	3.132	0.087	2.551	3.713
Integrational- Ethnonational: hybrid-External	3.008	3.008	0.100	2.386	3.629

Dependent Variable:
Joint emplacement
index

When, however, the three dimensions of the heritage participation patterns were correlated separately with the emplacement index, a significant relationship was depicted between the index values and the type of cultural heritage engagement – Integrational, Separative, Assimilationist and Marginalised. The Type significantly differentiated respondents on the index, both in its full version (four categories) and after removing categories with very low frequencies (marginalised and assimilationists with frequencies of four people each). Further descriptive analyses exclude types with low frequencies (marginalised and assimilationist). Respondents representing the integrational type had the highest average score on the joint index

(socio-cultural and structural dimensions combined) and this score was statistically significant. When dimensions of the index were separated into socio-cultural and structural, the variable Type also correlated significantly with the socio-cultural dimensions of the index. Interestingly, the relationship between the type and structural dimension of the index was not statistically significant, even though the average score for Integrational respondents is higher than for the respondents representing other types (Table 15).

In addition, logistic regression was conducted for a variable “type”, with a focus on two categories with satisfying frequencies – Integrational and Separative. As mentioned, the index was divided into two ranges (from 0 to <3 and from 3-6), and the probability of falling into each of the two categories was calculated. The calculated effect of the integrational type was very strong and statistically significant at the <0.01 level. The chances of the respondents representing this type of getting a score of 3 and above on the emplacement index were 2.5 times higher than those of other respondents. The effect of the Separative type was strong too and statistically significant at the <0.05 level. The chances of the respondents representing this type of getting a score of 3 and above were 61% lower than other respondents.

On the other hand, the characteristics, namely how people defined their cultural heritage practices, did not correlate with the index. Neither did motivation. This means that it is less important how people define their heritage and why they engage with heritage practices in the context of their score on the emplacement index, and more important whether they engage with new practices that are made into their heritage or not.

Table 15. Average index values across types.

Type	Joint emplacement index	Sociocultural emplacement index	Structural emplacement index
Integrational	3.0530	1.6017	1.4513
Assimilationist	2.3512	1.2679	1.0833
Separative	2.4846	1.3655	1.1190
Marginalised	2.5680	1.3196	1.2483
Total	2.8484	1.5119	1.3366

Discussion and Conclusions

The presented calculations bring several important findings. First of all, they show that people, who engage with new cultural heritage practices in the new homeland (integrational type) are better embedded into the new locations of their settlement (higher scores on the emplacement index) than those who do not engage with new cultural heritage practices, but rather stick to what they “brought” with them when migrating (Separative type). This may sound intuitive, but it brings important evidence that engagement in cultural heritage practices acquired *in* the new homeland is part of the emplacement process. The collected data does not allow conclusions about the direction of this influence, yet it shows that the emplacement and acquisition of cultural heritage practices in the new homeland are connected vessels and hence the cultural heritage of migrant people deserves attention in both academic and stakeholder approaches to the emplacement process of the migrants.

Significantly, it is less important how people define their cultural heritage practices – whether they see them as familial, or as tied to the traditions and modes of operating the ancestral or new homeland – and what matters is whether the respondents remained open and had an opportunity to engage with new cultural heritage practices in the new homeland – be it new homeland traditions, new habits encountered in the diaspora, or the individual acquisition of new elements of cultural heritage that happened as a result of negotiations between the known practices and the habits encountered in a new spatial and socio-cultural setting. It therefore shows that being engaged in new practices that are connected to the diaspora is potentially equally valuable in terms of the emplacement process, as engagement with the new homeland’s national heritage.

Last but not least, the structural emplacement index, even if not statistically significant in combination with the type dimension of cultural heritage participation patterns, was remarkably higher on average for people representing the *Integrational* type of heritage participation. It is important to underline that structural issues, especially economic ones, can stand as barriers to participation in culture and cultural heritage. Qualitative interviews showed that some respondents, in their most difficult financial moments in the new homeland, did not engage in cultural heritage activities out of lack of resources, e.g. to buy the products needed to prepare Christmas dishes. Therefore, based on qualitative analyses, I refrain from undermining the significance of structural emplacement for cultural heritage participation patterns.

Overall, the findings suggest that attention to cultural heritage in research on people's post-migration adaptation to the new place of settlement is needed as the cultural heritage engagement in the new homeland aligns with overall emplacement outcomes. In other words, cultural heritage participation seems to be a part of the emplacement process and seems to work according to the principle of connected vessels. It is therefore crucial to include reflections on the cultural heritage participation of those who migrate in the migration studies debates regarding the adaptation of migrants. Further research is needed to determine the direction of the relationship between cultural heritage participation patterns and the adaptation process.

From the perspective of heritage studies and heritage practice, cultural heritage participation is connected to the process of emplacement, making it worth investing time and resources into creating venues for cultural heritage-making by the migrants *in* the new homeland. As shown, in terms of the emplacement process, it is less important whether people call their heritage as primarily ethnically oriented or not, nor is it crucial for them to engage specifically with the national heritage of the new homeland. What matters, instead, is the engagement with new heritage practices in the new localities of settlement. Hence the focus in the field of heritage practice should shift towards creating opportunities for migrants to engage with the local heritage, to co-create new heritage practices with the locals (with and without migration background), as well as to renegotiate their premigration heritage practices within the new circumstances of the present.

Conclusions

This report presented the findings from the HerInt research. It described the goals of the research, its methodology and its sample. Then it moved to the analyses divided into three parts – the first one dedicated to the analyses of cultural policy towards minorities in Poland and Norway – the settlement countries of the project participants. The second part of the analysis was dedicated to the description of cultural heritage participation patterns that were created inductively based on the qualitative data collected. It also described the distribution of the types in the countries of settlement and the relationship between subsequent patterns and their categories with the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The third part of the analysis was dedicated to the description of the emplacement index created for the purpose of the research, its distribution in the sample, as well as the relationship between the emplacement index and the cultural heritage participation patterns.

Overall the report had three goals that are summed up in this section. It strived to present the modes of cultural heritage participation patterns by people who migrate, and it did so through the presentation of three-dimension cultural heritage participation patterns model. It described possible background characteristics and country-specific policies that potentially influenced the modes of participation in heritage among people post-migration. Finally, it attempted to establish and describe the relationship between the emplacement outcomes of individuals in relation to the post-migration settlement, and their modes of participation in cultural heritage.

The main conclusion that the conducted research brings is that cultural heritage participation patterns are connected to the emplacement outcomes, though not with relation to how people define their heritage, but rather in relation to their heritage practice oriented (or not) to the engagement with new heritage practices acquired post-migration. Those who indeed engaged with new heritage practices post-migration scored higher on average on the emplacement index than those who stuck to their pre-migration cultural heritage scripts only. This finding is of great importance, as it shows that what matters is the engagement with new heritage practices, regardless of the way people define them – as new homeland mainstream, ancestral homeland oriented, or relating to any other community identity. Therefore, it is less important how institutions and policies create the space for cultural heritage engagement of migrants, and more important is the fact that they actually do so.

On the other hand, country-specific policy can shape the ways people engage with heritage and especially how they define their heritage practices. The authorities, governments, institutions and stakeholders can therefore create a vision of a preferable mode of cultural heritage engagement with regard to the outcome they want to achieve, creating a strong policy that supports that vision. If their aim, however, is to support the emplacement of migrants through heritage practices, the focus does not need to be placed on any essentialist ideas relating to ethnic, national, local or any other heritage. Instead, the effort should be put into creating spaces for heritage celebration, co-creation and inclusion, as this will further support engaging with heritage practices encountered in the new homeland. This is because emplacement and engagement with heritage practices in the new homeland are connected vessels, while the characteristic of this engagement is less important for the emplacement outcomes.

This research was not able to identify the direction of the relationship between cultural heritage participation patterns and individual emplacement based on statistical correlation. It did, however, establish the fact that the two are interconnected. It is clear that people who are better

adapted to and emplaced in the new homeland might be more prone to engage with locally encountered new forms of heritage. The presented qualitative analyses show that engagement with local heritage in the new homeland can create meaningful connections that play a significant role in socio-cultural emplacement. It fosters building social relationships in the new locality of settlement, develops belonging and helps re-negotiate identity in relation to the new spatial and socio-cultural settings in the new country. Therefore, heritage should not be overlooked in analyses of the emplacement process. Although intuitive, this has not been a popular approach in mainstream migration research, which has tended to focus on the adaptation of migrating people, while this report proved that this omission obscured an important aspect of the emplacement process and should be addressed in further research.

Policy Recommendations

The data presented in this report allowed for the formulation of four recommendations for policymakers regarding the employment of cultural heritage as a means to foster migrants' emplacement to the local socio-spatial contexts:

1. If the goal is to enhance emplacement through cultural heritage participation, then pushing minority groups into mainstream heritage activities exclusively does not enhance emplacement. It may, however, influence the way people define their heritage practices, but for the emplacement process, it is not of particular significance.
2. To enhance emplacement, create and implement policies that support integrational heritage participation patterns, as they correlate with the most extended emplacement outcomes. This may include opening up the mainstream heritage to minorities, but also creating venues to produce new forms of heritage, as explained further.
3. Create venues for heritage engagement, prioritising spaces that allow migrants to co-create cultural heritage with other locals – both representing the mainstream population and those with migration and minority backgrounds.

4. Shift the focus of current policies on an official and field level from one oriented on labelling the heritage that minorities should become part of, to one that provides for common co-creation spaces where people can engage freely with heritage and create new forms of heritage locally. This approach can strengthen the sense of belonging among new inhabitants, positively influencing their emplacement process.

Acknowledgements

This project has received generous funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, grant agreement No 101059766.

I would like to thank everyone who contributed to this research, either by taking part in the study or supporting subsequent stages of the research project within the framework of the HerInt research team. Thanks are due to the research assistants who helped collect and transcribe the interviews (Jagoda Krajewska, Yana Hurtova, Klaudia Błaszczak, Ada Iwanowicz, Aleksandra Luranc, Kinga Blacha, and Kamila Bulanda) and who ran statistical analyses (Karolina Zawadzka and Patrycja Pyra).

The data was processed using the PS IMAGO PRO solution, whose analytical engine is IBM SPSS Statistics.

References

- Anthias, F. (2008). Thinking through the Lens of Translocational Positionality: an Intersectionality Frame for Understanding Identity and Belonging. *Translocations: Migration and Social Change*, 4(1), 5–20.
- Appiah, Anthony K., and Amy Gutmann. (1996) *Color Conscious: The Political Morality of Race*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Arokiasamy, C. (2012). Embedding Shared Heritage: the Cultural Heritage Rights of London's African and Asian Diaspora Communities. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 18(3), 339–345.
- Balibar, É. (1991). Is There a Neo-Racism? In: É. Balibar and I. Wallerstein (Eds.). *Race, Nation, Class: Ambiguous Identities* (pp. 17–28). London: Verso.
- Banaszkiewicz, M. & K. Nikielska-Sekuła (Eds.). (2024). *Cultural Heritage and Mobility from a Multisensory Perspective*. London: Routledge.
- Bivand Erdal, M., & Oeppen, C. (2013). Migrant balancing acts: Understanding the interactions between integration and transnationalism. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 39(6), 867-884.
- Bodo, S. (2012). Museums as Intercultural Spaces. In: R. Sandell and E. Nightingale (Eds.), *Museums, Equality and Social Justice* (pp. 181–191). New York and London: Routledge.
- Brochmann, G., & Hagelund, A. (2012). Norway: The Land of the Golden Mean. In G. Brochman & A. Hagelund (Eds.), *Immigration Policy and the Scandinavian Welfare State 1946–2010* (pp. 149–224). London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Brunarska, Z., Kindler, M., Szulecka, M., & Toruńczyk-Ruiz, S. (2016). Ukrainian migration to Poland: a “local” mobility? In Fedyuk, O., & Kindler, M. *Ukrainian Migration to the European Union: Lessons from Migration Studies* (pp. 115-131). Amsterdam: Springer Nature.
- Byrne, D. (2016). Heritage Corridors: Transnational Flows and the Built Environment of Migration. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 42 (14), 2360–2378.
- Çağlar, A. (1997). Hyphenated Identities and the Limits of ‘Culture’: Some Methodological Queries. In P. Werbner & T. Madood (Eds.), *The Politics of Multiculturalism in the New Europe: Racism, Identity, Community* (pp. 169–185). New York: Zed Publications.
- Çağlar, A., & Glick Schiller, N. (2015). A multiscalar perspective on cities and migration: A comment on the symposium. *Sociologica*, 9(2), 0-0.

- Çağlar, A., & Glick Schiller, N. (2018). *Migrants and city-making: Dispossession, displacement, and urban regeneration*. Duke University Press.
- Çağlar, A., & Glick Schiller, N. (2023). Relational multiscalar analysis: a comparative approach to migrants within city-making processes. In F. Hillmann & M. Samers (Eds.), *Cities, Migration, and Governance* (pp. 40-66). London: Routledge.
- Colomer, L., & Holtorf, C. (2018). What is cross-cultural heritage?: Challenges in identifying the heritage of globalized citizens. In C. Holtorf, A. Pantazatos, G. Scarre (Eds.), *Cultural heritage, ethics and contemporary migrations* (pp. 147-164). London: Routledge.
- Colomer, L., (2017). Heritage on the move. Cross-cultural heritage as a response to globalisation, mobilities and multiple migrations. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 23 (10), 913–927.
- De Haas, H., & Fokkema, T. (2011). The effects of integration and transnational ties on international return migration intentions. *Demographic research*, 25, 755–782.
- Faist, T. (2004). The Transnational Turn in Migration Research: Perspectives for the Study of Politics and Polity. In M. P. Frykman, *Transnational Spaces: Disciplinary Perspectives* (pp. 11–45). Malmö: Malmö University.
- Fangen, K. (2006a). Assimilert, hybrid eller inkorporert i det etniske? Tilpasning og identifikasjon blant somaliere i Norge. *Sosiologisk tidsskrift*, 14(1), 4–33.
- Fangen, K. (2006b). Humiliation Experienced by Somali Refugees in Norway. *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 19(1), 69–93.
- Fangen, K. (2007a). Breaking Up the Different Constituting Parts of Ethnicity: The Case of Young Somalis in Norway. *Acta Sociologica*, 50(4), 401–414.
- Gulbrandsen, F., A. S. Kulasingam, C. Sørlien Molstad, and A. Steinkellner. (2021). *Innvandrere og norskfødte med innvandrerforeldres fordeling på kommunenivå* Report of Statistisk sentralbyrå. Oslo: Statistics Norway.
- Geschiere, P. (2009). *The Perils of Belonging: Autochthony, Citizenship, and Exclusion in Africa and Europe*. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press.
- Glick Schiller, N., & Çağlar, A. (2013). Locating migrant pathways of economic emplacement: Thinking beyond the ethnic lens. *Ethnicities*, 13(4), 494-514.
- Glick Schiller, N., & Çağlar, A. (2016). Displacement, emplacement and migrant newcomers: Rethinking urban sociabilities within multiscalar power. *Identities*, 23(1), 17-34.

- Gnecco, C., (2015). Heritage in Multicultural Times. In: E. Waterton and S. Watson (Eds.), *The Palgrave Handbook of Contemporary Heritage Research*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 263–280.
- Górny, A., Kaczmarczyk, P., Inglis, C., Li, W., & Khandria, B. (2019). European migration transition in the context of post-enlargement migration from and into Central and Eastern Europe. In C. Inglis, W. Li, B. Khadria (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of international migration* (pp. 358-375), Sage.
- Greiner, C., & P. Sakdapolrak. (2013). Translocality: Concepts, Applications and Emerging Research Perspectives. *Geography Compass* 7 (5), 373–84.
- Gupta, A. & Ferguson, J. (2008). Beyond ‘Culture’: Space, Identity, and the Politics of Difference. In: T. Oakes & P.L. Price (Eds.), *The Cultural Geography Reader*. London: Routledge, 72–79.
- Harrison, R., C. DeSilvey, C. Holtorf & S. Macdonald (2020). For Ever, for Everyone... . In: Harrison, R., DeSilvey, C., Holtorf, C., Macdonald, S., Bartolini, N., Breithoff, E. (Eds.), *Heritage Futures: Comparative Approaches to Natural and Cultural Heritage Practices* (pp. 3–19). London: UCL Press.
- Harvey, D.C. (2001). Heritage Pasts and Heritage Presents: Temporality, Meaning and the Scope of Heritage Studies. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 7 (4), 319–338.
- Holtorf, C., Pantazatos, A., & Scarre, G. (Eds.). (2018). *Cultural heritage, ethics and contemporary migrations*. London: Routledge.
- Innocenti, P. (Ed.). (2014). *Migrating Heritage: Experiences of Cultural Networks and Cultural Dialogue in Europe*. Surrey: Ashgate.
- Leung, C.K.Y. (2006). Usable Pasts, Staging Belongings: Articulating a ‘Heritage’ of Multiculturalism in Canada. *Studies in Ethnicity and Nationalism*, 6 (2), 162–179.
- Levitt, P., & N. Glick Schiller. (2004). Conceptualizing Simultaneity: A Transnational Social Field Perspective on Society. *International Migration Review* 38 (3): 1002–39.
- Lixinski, L. (2023). Cultural heritage and interculturality: a call to action. *International journal of heritage studies*, 29, 1361–1373.
- Macdonald, S., (2013). *Memorylands. Heritage and Identity in Europe*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Mohamed, A. & Holtorf, C. (n.d.) The challenges of Somali Cultural Heritage for the dominant discourse in Sweden. Unpublished conference paper.

- Mucha, J. (2021). Integration of Migrants in a Major Polish City. Kraków's Public Cultural Institutions and the "New Ukrainians". *Studia Migracyjne-Przegląd Polonijny*, (3), 269-292.
- Nettleford, R. (2004). Migration, transmission and maintenance of the intangible heritage. *Museum International*, 56(1-2), 78-83.
- Neyrinck, J. (2017). Intangible cultural heritage in times of 'superdiversity': Exploring ways of transformation. *International Journal of Intangible Heritage*, 12, 158-174.
- Nikielska-Sekula, K. (2018). *Locating In-betweenness Belonging, Translocational Positionality, and the Cultural Heritage of Drammenian Turks*. PhD thesis, University of South-Eastern Norway.
- Nikielska-Sekuła, K. (2023). Embodied transnational belonging. *International Migration Review* 0(0).
- Nikielska-Sekula, K., & Desille, A. (2021). *Visual methodology in migration studies: New possibilities, theoretical implications, and ethical questions*. Amsterdam: Springer Nature.
- Nikielska-Sekula, K., (2019). Migrating heritage? Recreating ancestral and new homeland heritage in the practices of immigrant minorities. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 25 (11), 1113–1127.
- Phillimore, J., & Goodson, L. (2008). Making a place in the global city: The relevance of indicators of integration. *Journal of refugee studies*, 21(3), 305-325.
- Prescott, C. (2018). Changing demographics and cultural heritage in Northern Europe: Transforming narratives and identifying obstacles: a case study from Oslo, Norway. In Holtorf, C., Pantazatos, A., & Scarre, G. (Eds.). *Cultural heritage, ethics and contemporary migrations* (pp. 52-69). London: Routledge.
- Smith, L. (2016). *Uses of Heritage*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Smith, L. (2021). *Emotional Heritage*. New York: Routledge.
- SSB Statistics Norway. 2024. Available at ssb.no (accessed 21.10.2024).
- Van der Zeijden, A., & Elpers, S. (2017). Intangible heritage & the museum in an age of superdiversity. *IMP Intangible cultural heritage & museums project*.
- Van Hear, N., Brubaker, R. & Bessa, T. (2009) Managing Mobility for Human Development: The Growing Salience of Mixed Migration, No HDRP-2009-20, Human Development Research Papers (2009 to present), Human Development Report Office (HDRO), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), available at:

<https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:hdp:papers:hdp-2009-20>
21.10.2024).

(accessed

Wessendorf, S., & Phillimore, J. (2019). New migrants' social integration, embedding and emplacement in superdiverse contexts. *Sociology*, 53(1), 123-138.

Wikan, U. (1999). Culture: a new concept of race. *Social anthropology*, 7 (1), 57–64.

Wimmer, A. & Glick Schiller, N. (2002). Methodological nationalism and beyond: nation-state building, migration and the social sciences. *Global networks*, 2 (4), 301–334.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Source cultural policy documents analysed in subsequent countries

Poland, sourced at: gov.pl, isap.sej.gov.pl

- Polityka Kulturalna Państwa - Założenia (August 1993)
- Zadania Ministerstwa Kultury i Sztuki 1995–1997 (1994)
- Karta Kultury Polskiej (february 1997)
- Kierunki polityki kulturalnej rządu (March 1999)
- Narodowa Strategia Rozwoju Kultury 2004-2013 (2004)
- Narodowa Strategia Rozwoju Kultury 2004-2020 - uzupełnienie (2005)
- Pakiet dla Dziedzictwa Narodowego (March 2007)
- Strategia Rozwoju Kapitału Społecznego 2020 (2013)
- Strategia na rzecz Odpowiedzialnego Rozwoju (2017)

Norway, sourced at: regjeringen.no

- Rom for deltakelse 2023-2025
- Kunstnarkår 2022-2023
- Oppleve, skape, dele 2020-21
- Frivilligheita – sterk, sjølvstendig, mangfaldig 2018-2019
- Kulturens kraft 2018-2019
- Kultur, inkludering og deltaking 2011-2012
- Visuell kunst (2011-2012)
- Kulturutredningen 2014 (2013)
- Kulturpolitikk fram mot 2014 (2002-2003)

Appendix 2:

EMPLACEMENT INDEX (*marks/points listed next to the answer; -8 – irrelevant/do not count*)

I. Structural emplacement outcomes

1. Participation in the labour market

a) Do you work?

- a. Yes – above my qualifications – 3
- b. Yes – according to my qualifications (or parallel level) – 2
- c. Yes – under my qualifications – 1
- d. No – 0

2. Education

a) Have you participated in formal education in your new homeland? (marking the highest score only)

- a. Yes – I have studied/ attended high/primary/secondary school in the new homeland – 3
- b. Yes – I have had professional courses in the new homeland – 2
- c. Yes – I have had language courses in the new homeland – 1
- d. No – 0

3. Citizenship

a) Do you have citizenship of your new homeland?

- a. Yes – 3
- b. No, but I have applied for it – 2
- c. No, but I plan to apply for it (also I will apply when I can) – 1
- d. No and I do not plan to apply for it – 0

II. Socio-cultural integration

1. Do you have social ties **in** your locality of settlement

- a) Yes, in my new locality of settlement I have: family ties/ a friends circle/ ties with people in hobby/thematic groups (including religious groups, and parenting groups...)/ ties through work/education, ties through neighbourhood relationships – 1 point for each group
- b) marriage/ partnership with a person met here:
 - a) no – 0
 - b) yes – in relationship – 1
 - c) yes – married – 2

2. Identification and Belonging

- a) How many groups do you identify with **in** the new homeland:
- 1 point for each strong group identification, 0.5- weak identification
- b) What is your self-identification? – 1 point for each self-identification connected to the identities **located in** the new homeland
- c) Do you feel at home in the new locality of settlement?
- a) Yes – 3
 - b) Sometimes/ to some extent – 2
 - c) Rather not – 1
 - d) No – 0
- d) Do you think you and your cultural practices are accepted in the new homeland?
- a) Yes – 3
 - b) Sometimes/ to some extent – 2
 - c) Rather not – 1
 - d) No – 0
- e) Do you think you are well integrated into the new homeland society
- a) Yes – 3
 - b) Rather yes – 2
 - c) Rather not – 1
 - d) No – 0

3. Cultural adaptation

- a) Do you speak the mainstream language of the new homeland?
- a) Yes – proficiently – 4
 - b) Yes – advanced – 3
 - c) Yes – communicative – 2
 - d) Yes – basic – 1
 - e) No – 0
- b) Do you participate in cultural events in the new homeland (cinema, theatre, etc.)? (only the highest score)
- a) Yes – mainstream 3

- b) Yes – organised by mainstream institutions for minorities – 2
- c) Yes – organised by minority organisations – 1
- d) No – 0

Appendix 3 Interview guide (translated from Polish by the author)

1. Think about the people who are important to you – those you stay in touch with or contact daily or regularly (whether they live nearby or the contact is held online). Draw a map of your relationships. Do not use names; simply describe them as "sister, family, friend..." Now, indicate where they live.

2. Who are you – not in terms of your age or job, but in terms of how you see yourself? What is important for you?

3. Please tell me about your cultural heritage – about the practices, traditions, language, stories, or food that are part of your daily life and that you consider important because they have made you who you are. /Do you have any photos that show your traditions, meaningful objects, places, people, or dishes we're talking about? / Who do you share these practices with? (referring to the relationship map from question 1).

[allow respondents to go through the photos they prepared and talk about their depictions, then, check if all aspects detailed below were covered – if not, ask about them]

Auxiliary questions – ask about aspects that have not been addressed. For each question, inquire about photos showcasing these practices –

2a. Tell us about the traditions you nurture/cultivate. Where and with whom do you celebrate?

2b. Are there any activities you learned in your home country, for example, from a family member, that have been passed down from generation to generation? Do you practice them here where you live?

2c. Are there any activities you intentionally taught yourself to be able to maintain your traditions here where you live? Are there any local traditions that you practice in your home?

2d. Do you have any items that hold sentimental value for you, or are important because they somehow define you? Tell me about them—where are they?

2f. Are there any scents, landscapes, tastes, or sensations that you consider important because they represent who you are/constitute elements that can be seen as part of your cultural heritage or make you feel at home? Please, describe them.

Are there scents, tastes or landscapes in your new homeland that feel foreign to you and remind you that you are not from here? Or are there any unpleasant experiences that you've gotten used to over time and they no longer bother you?

2g. Tell us about your culinary habits – what do you eat, how do you cook? Do you make preserves? What kind? Where do you get your recipes from?

2h. What language/languages do you use and in what circumstances? (What languages do you use at home, with your children, partner, at work, with friends... etc.)

2i. What kind of music do you like and listen to?

2j. *Carefully ask, and if emotions arise, withdraw:* Do you use national symbols? Which ones? In what circumstances? Where? What do these symbols mean to you?

3. Do you go to the cinema, theatre, concerts, dances, museums, festivals, picnics for foreigners, workshops, language cafes, children's events, etc?

3a. What events do you choose, and does the language of the event matter in your decision?

4. Where do you feel at home? Why? What practices are important to you for a place to feel like home?

5. Do you feel that your cultural practices are accepted where you live? Do people in your new homeland ask you about your customs from ancestral homeland?

6. Do you feel integrated? Do you feel that you have adapted to your new local society? (Why? In which aspects yes, in which no...)

7. Which groups in your new locality (new country) do you identify with/feel a connection to?

8. Now, on your map of social relationships, write down with whom you practice each tradition/cultural practice.
(For the respondent's convenience, you can summarise the practices they have mentioned.)

Appendix 4 Background questionnaire

1. Gender:
2. Birth year:
3. How many years/months have you been living in Poland (in total):
4. In which year did you first come to Poland for purposes other than tourism or leisure?:.....
5. Do you work?
6. What is your trained profession?
7. What is your current occupation?
8. Education obtained in your home country (primary, lower secondary/vocational, higher):
.....
9. Education obtained in your new homeland (primary, secondary/vocational, higher, NA)
.....
10. Education obtained in another country:
 - a. Level:.....
 - b. Country:.....
11. Do you speak the mainstream new homeland's language?
12. At what level? Fluent/Very good/ Communicative/ Weak
13. Do you have children?
 - a. How many:.....
 - b. Age:.....
14. Do you have a partner?
15. Do you live together?
16. If not, in which country does your partner live?
17. Do you have Polish citizenship / do you plan to have it? I DO NOT HAVE AND DO NOT PLAN TO / I DO NOT HAVE, BUT I PLAN TO / I HAVE IT.
18. Where do you live (city and population)
19. Where did you move from? (city and population)